

TOYLABS

ENABLING AN OPEN INNOVATION MODEL FOR EU TOY INDUSTRY SMES
 THROUGH CO-CREATION WITH FABLABS, SAFETY EXPERTS AND CUSTOMER
 COMMUNITIES
 732559

EXPLORING PROGRESS AND INNOVATION IN TOYLABS TACKLED DOMAINS AND TOYLABS CONCEPT DEFINITION

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ABSTRACT

The main purpose of this deliverable is to analyse the requirements of the toy industry in order to adapt the TOYLABS concept by considering the needs of toy companies.

In order to achieve this goal, in part A of this deliverable, design and manufacturing processes, technologies and techniques were studied.

In part B, two important strategies for TOYLAB success were explained, collaborative design and market and design research.

In part C, the TOYLAB requirements were identified, by considering the main problems the toy industry encounters when developing new products and the services most valued by toy companies as a starting point to develop the first approach towards defining the TOYLABS concept.

It should be considered that this deliverable constitutes qualitative exploratory research, with in-depth analysis of toy manufacturing processes and needs, to support the definition of a TOYLAB. Although it cannot be considered to be a representation of the entire European toy industry, it could be a starting point for future studies or projects.

1 INTRODUCTION

The toy market in the EU (and globally) is characterised by the domination of a limited number of huge global brands, even though 99% of EU toy manufacturing companies are SMEs. Thus, SMEs need to find new ways to strengthen their position, against large competitors. In this context, ToyLabs envisions introducing a new model that will innovate the value network of SMEs, in the direction of changing their market positioning & prospects in the toy industry, overcoming obstacles like geographical barriers and fragmented markets.

In particular, a multi-stakeholder co-creation network will be created, supported via an open ICT platform, that will bring together a toy manufacturer with other key players of the toy industry value network – FabLabs, Toy Security Experts and End Customers – to collaborate closely in order to provide new toys, that will be user-oriented, will respond to a clear market demand and will probably be addressed to multiple markets.

Through the ToyLabs approach, each stakeholder involved is expected to offer their valuable perspective that will open up new opportunities for SMEs. Taking advantage of the platform, a toy manufacturer will be able to collect multi-source feedback on new product concepts & designs, through iterative cycles where the initial idea is firstly co-designed with FabLabs, validated by toy safety experts and evaluated by prospective customers, both virtually (via augmented reality technologies) and in reality (based on prototypes).

2 OVERALL APPROACH AND METHODOLOGY

The overall aim of this research is to collate the requirements that will enable ToyLabs to offer a service and tools that are aligned with stakeholders involved in the toy sector. A further objective is to obtain an overview of design and manufacturing processes in toy companies today.

The next section describes the methodology of this study in detail.

2.1 DESK RESEARCH

Desk Research methodology is part of market research and involves the collection and analysis of data from secondary sources, i.e., information previously published by others. It is based on documentary sources, both internal and external, websites, books, magazines, media, blogs, articles, studies and reports published by various organisations. Its purpose is to obtain a better knowledge of the subject of the project (AIJU, 2016).

Academic and non-academic sources were used in order to obtain inputs. Desk Research methodology has been carried out to elaborate the following information:

- Determining the state-of-the-art and best practices regarding collaborative development approaches in the manufacturing sector (Section 6)
- Determining the state-of-the-art regarding which technologies are offering FabLabs in Europe today. (Section 8.4)
- Elaborating the initial hypothesis about design and manufacturing processes in the toy sector (Section 3.3.1)
- Developing the design of the questionnaire (Annex 2)
- Determining the state-of-the-art regarding design process (Section 3.2)

In order to determine the design processes in the toy sector and identify the problems, needs and opportunities for ToyLabs, several tasks were performed:

- First, a review of the state-of-the-art of design processes is presented in order to understand the evolution and development of design process methodologies, illustrate the main phases in design processes and how they are named.
- Second, a comparative analysis was made detecting differences and similarities between the different toy companies interviewed for this project.

- Third, the toy-manufacturing model was compared with previous literature.
- Fourth, the importance of the different activities related with the toy-manufacturing processes was analysed.
- Finally, the problems, needs, and opportunities for ToyLabs were identified.

2.2 SURVEY

2.2.1 Methodology

The online survey was carried out to gather existing and emerging processes and techniques in manufacturing. Fieldwork was performed in March and April 2017; analysis was completed on 43 returned surveys. Respondents were recruited through AIJU's database. AIJU's database is a collection of data on professionals from companies related to the children's sector who are interested in participating in studies that AIJU carries out.

Survey guidelines

The structure of the questionnaire is explained below:

1. Introduction. First, a text was included to express gratitude for participating in the study, explaining the purpose and verifying that participation was voluntary.
2. Classification data. Stakeholders were asked some professional questions: profile, name of the organisation and country where they work, country where the company carries out both the design and manufacturing processes, and the category of products manufactured by the company.
3. Production process. Stakeholders were asked whether the activities were carried out internally or outsourced. Respondents were also asked about the level of importance of these activities.
4. Toy category characterisation. For the toy category selected, respondents were asked about the raw materials used in their products. This question acted as a filter so that, for each raw material used, respondents were asked about the manufacturing and finishing processes used.
5. Toy company needs. Stakeholders were asked about the problems and obstacles that they encounter when developing and manufacturing new products. Concerning technologies, they were asked which technologies they were considering acquiring in the near future.
6. Thanks expressed for participation.

Figure 1. Questionnaire screenshot.

	INSIDE THE COMPANY	OUTSOURCED	NOT DONE	DO NOT KNOW/NO OPINION
Briefing – strategic definition, project generation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Idea generation and concept definition	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Product design	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Prototype development	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Quality	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
User test	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Marketing content development	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Product engineering	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Cost analysis	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Price strategy	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Product presentation – internal and external	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Forecast – estimation of number of units to produce	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
mould development	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other (please specify)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

2.2.2 Pilot test

To ensure that the protocols, methodology and data collection systems were appropriate for the survey objectives, a pilot phase of the study was performed with a sample of 4 experts and 3 companies. Following this pilot test, the methodology was adjusted.

Minor changes were the following:

- Ask for continents instead of countries in order to make the questionnaire shorter.
- Regarding the raw materials used in the products manufactured, an “Electric and electronic components” response option was added.
- Specific manufacturing processes regarding textiles were added.

Major changes were the following:

- Information and consent letter were reduced.
- New key activities were added regarding the activity performed in the company when producing the products.

2.2.3 Ethical values

Ethical values were used to carry out this research. Each stakeholder was assigned an identification code in order to ensure anonymity.

Respondents were provided with information so they had a better understanding of the main purpose of the study process. The information letter can be found in Annex 1. Additionally, a consent form was developed for respondents in order to guarantee compliance with all ethical areas: informed consent, authorisation for gathering the information and for transferring the rights to the information to the ToyLab European Project (Annex 1).

2.2.4 Sample description

Below is the description of the toy companies sample in terms of toy category, size and type of company and respondent profile.

Sample by toy category

The online questionnaire was carried out in Spain and, with a reduced response, in the rest of Europe. A total of 43 respondents from companies in the toy sector answered the questionnaire.

The toy categories for companies in the online survey was elaborated following CEN CR14379 (2002). A complete list can be consulted in the questionnaire in Annex 2. Figure 2 shows the toy category sample description. The industry with the highest participation was the dolls and soft-filled toy category, and that of game sets -picture dominoes, simple matching games, board games, bingo, etc.-.

Figure 2. Sample description regarding category of products.

Q. Please select the category of products manufactured by your company. If your company manufactures in more than one category, please select the one with the highest number of units produced

Below are the other toy categories of participants in the online survey and their scope:

- Skill development toys (stacking blocks, shape sorters, sewing kits, modelling sets, etc.)
- Mechanical and/or electrical driven vehicles (not intended to bear the mass of a child: trains that make noise, pull-back vehicles, track racing sets, action figure vehicles, etc.)
- Arts and crafts materials and related articles (crayons, chalks, pens, scissors, etc.)
- Construction toys and puzzles
- Role-playing toys (for imitation of adult activities: toy telephones, play dishes and tea sets, doll shopping carts, etc.)
- Toys intended to bear the mass of a child (toy scooters, rocking horses, pedal cars, etc.)
- Sand-water toys (sand tools with simple shapes, watering cans, plastic cars/vans, radio-controlled boats/ships, etc.)
- Play scenes and constructed models (farms, garages, dollhouses, detailed and realistic cars, puppet theatres, etc.)
- Projectile toys with launching device (toys that eject balls, bows and arrows, etc.)
- Activity toys (swings, slides, gym set, etc.)
- Toy musical instruments

Sample by company size

The size of a company was determined by its turnover:

- Micro: Companies with less than €2 million turnover
- Small: Companies between €2 and €9.99 million turnover
- Medium: Companies between €10 and €49.99 million turnover
- Large: Companies with €50 million or more turnover

Figure 3. Sample description regarding company size.

As is the case in the total toy sector, the sample profile has a higher proportion of micro and small companies (Figure 3).

Sample by profile of respondent

The survey was answered by the following working profiles: manager, production, quality control, research and development and administration (Figure 4)

Figure 4. Sample description regarding respondent profile.

Q. Please indicate your profile (multiple choice)

2.3 PERSONAL INTERVIEW

After conducting a questionnaire with 43 participants, the next stage and main objective was to organise and conduct a series of interviews with Spanish and European toy companies to obtain a more in-depth understanding of their design and manufacturing processes, as well as the needs and services which ToyLabs should provide.

The secondary objective of the interviews was to assist ToyLab partner NTUA with task 1.3 'Stakeholders Requirements and High-level Usage Scenarios'. The insights gathered from personal interviews could further help define user requirements and the design of the platform's features.

2.3.1 Methodology

The personal interview was carried out to obtain a more in-depth understanding of their design and manufacturing processes, as well as the needs and services which ToyLabs should provide. Fieldwork was performed in March and April 2017; 13 personal interviews were conducted in Spanish toy companies. Respondents were recruited through AIJU's database¹. Communication was established by email and telephone

Interview guidelines

A semi-structured approach enables a dialogue and deep engagement with the participant while retaining focus on a particular topic. In order to manage this semi-structured approach, simplify the collection of data, and make the process more visual and friendly, template sheets were created (Figure 5).

¹ AIJU's database is a collection of data on professionals from companies related to child sector interested in participating in studies that AIJU carries out.

Figure 5. Example of a sheet used during the personal interviews.

Prior to each interview, data protection signature was asked. The structure of the personal interview is explained below:

1. Company profile. First, basic corporate data and information –date, user name, profile– was gathered for each participating company.
2. Productive process. Stakeholders were asked an open question about their company’s design and manufacturing process. Also, some specific questions were asked.
3. Toy company needs. Concerning the process described previously, stakeholders were asked about the problems and needs for each stage.
4. Fablab concept. After explaining the FabLab concept and making sure it was understood, respondents were asked about their awareness of FabLabs, and if they agreed with them.
5. ToyLab concept. After explaining the ToyLab concept and making sure it was understood, respondents were asked about which services and technologies a ToyLab should provide. Also, questions were asked about the ToyLabs customer journey and appeal.

2.3.2 Pilot test

To ensure that the protocols, methodology and data collection systems were appropriate for the personal interview objectives, a pilot phase of the study was performed with a sample of 2 experts and 2 companies. Following this pilot test, the methodology was adjusted.

Generally, the first version of personal interview is based on seeking deeper information of manufacturing processes, following online survey answers. After the pilot test, researchers decided to focus the objectives on gathering complementary information. The information required was that necessary to obtain a first approach of what a ToyLab should offer and organise. To achieve this goal, the aim of the personal interview was to determine the design and manufacturing process from the stage of ideation and conceptualisation of a new product to its production, and also the problems encountered when carrying out these activities in developing new products. The major changes made were the following:

- The positive and negative aspects of the manufacturing processes selected by the respondent in the online survey was eliminated.
- Prospective questions regarding manufacturing processes were eliminated.
- Questions focusing on design and manufacturing processes and their problems were added.
- Information and consent letter were reduced.

2.3.3 Ethical values

Ethical values were used to carry out this research. Each stakeholder was assigned an identification code in order to ensure anonymity.

Respondents were provided with information so they had a better understanding of the main purpose of the study process. The information letter can be found in Annex 1. Additionally, a consent form was developed for respondents in order to guarantee compliance with all ethical areas: informed consent, authorisations for gathering the information and for transferring the rights to the information to the ToyLab European Project (Annex 1).

2.3.4 Sample description

A mix of different toy category companies were agreed to take part in the personal interviews. The criteria for the companies selected for the study was that they be relevant toy companies in Spain and an international company member of the project consortium, regarding their presence in the market, and covering the different company profiles.

In the same way, toy companies represented a variety of toy categories. A list of companies that met the requirements was made, and contact was established with them via both email and telephone. The total sample size for the interviews was 13 participants. There were from: AEFJ -Asociación Española de Fabricantes de Juguetes-, the Spanish Toy Manufacturers Association; one toy distributor with their own product; and 11 manufactures of various toy categories. The profile of the

people interviewed were: Managers, RD directors, Designers directors, Marketing directors, expansion manager and Production director.

PART A: TOY COMPANIES DESIGN AND MANUFACTURING PROCESSES, TECHNOLOGIES AND TECHNIQUES

3 DESIGN AND MANUFACTURING PROCESSES IN THE TOY SECTOR

3.1 LOCATION OF PRODUCT DESIGN AND MANUFACTURING ACTIVITIES

Figure 6 and Figure 7 show the location of both design and manufacturing processes of the toy industry participants in the online survey. While the design process is accomplished almost entirely in Europe, the manufacturing task is accomplished between Europe and Asia.

Figure 6. Product design location.

Q. Select the continent where your company carries out product design (multiple choice)

Figure 7. Manufacturing location.

Q. Select the continent where your company manufactures (multiple choice)

Although the development of product design in Asia and America is very low, it is interesting to take it into account and study its evolution, in order to determine whether this fact could signify a trend change in industrial relocation. In this line, the analysis of the data gathered from toy companies, and AIJU's knowledge, draw the scenario explained below.

3.2 DESIGN PROCESS IN THE TOY SECTOR

In-depth research from questionnaires, personal interviews and secondary sources was useful to determine how toy companies manage the design process. Although there are differences in the way that the companies address their processes, a general workflow can be defined.

3.2.1 Design process literature review

Different organisations and Design Schools have various alternative structures and, therefore, names for describing the design process stages.

In this section, three of the most international approaches – d.school (Stanford), IDEO and Design Council – are described with the objective of forming a starting point to illustrate how design processes can be managed.

d.school- Stanford

The d.school Design Process is based on human-centred design to create innovative solutions to a problem. In this model the design process is divided into five different stages – Empathize, Define, Ideate, Prototype and Test ² – (Figure 8)

Figure 8. d.school's user-centred design process.

² The University of British Columbia. Vancouver Campus. Design Processes. Recovered from: <http://dstudio.ubc.ca/research/toolkit/processes/>

Empathize: Is the core philosophy under the HCD process. At this stage, the experts carry out in-depth research about the people or the target group that is going to be addressed with the new product or service. The study has the main objective of determining their physical and emotional needs – how they think, their insights, etc. – all the information relevant to create designs that are both useful and meaningful to people.

Define: The goal of this stage is the definition of a meaningful and actionable problem statement, bringing clarity and focus to the design project. The design team pays special attention to the definition of the challenge that the project presents, based on the available information about the users and their context.

This stage is about making sense of the information that was gathered in the previous stage. At this moment, experts analyse the information about the user through in-depth research. They share the results with other colleagues to work on defining some conclusions, actionable problem statements that unify the team and serve as the basis for ideating new solutions.

Ideate: This stage is focused on generating ideas, a stage before building prototypes. Beyond obvious solutions, the team ideates possible innovative solutions and options in a visual way. Once multiple ideas have been generated, the proposals are filtered before moving on to the next step. The common variables to determine the selection of the ideas that pass on to the next step are: Viability (concerning the reality of the business), Desirability (concerning how people value the product or service) and Feasibility (concerning the possibilities of the product or service to be implemented with the resources available).

Prototype: In this stage, the ideas become visible and usually tangible with the creation of prototypes. Prototypes are things created to simulate the final solution in a way that the team can test the solution as they allow the user to interact with it. The first prototypes are usually cheap and simple, and tend to evolve into more complex and detailed solutions.

Test: In this stage, the team gets feedback from the users that are testing the prototype. Both stages of Testing and Empathy are focused on understanding the target population; however, in the Testing stage, the problem or the framework is more concrete, tangible, and can be based on prototypes. The relevance of this stage is that designers can obtain highly valuable feedback from the user about what elements of the solution work for them, and which not³. All this data is of great

³ Hasso Platner (2010), Institute of Design at Stanford. An introduction to the design Thinking. Process Guide".
<https://dschool-old.stanford.edu/sandbox/groups/designresources/wiki/36873/attachments/74b3d/ModeGuideB OOTCAMP2010L.pdf?sessionID=1b6a96f1e2a50a3b1b7c3f09e58c40a062d7d553>

use when designing the final solution in a way that can really respond to the needs of the target.

IDEO Social

In 2009, IDEO created the "Human Centered Design Toolkit", with a clear objective to have a direct impact on the social sector⁴. In 2015, IDEO updated it to a new version called "The Field Guide to Human-Centered Design".

The HCD Toolkit was conceived to create new solutions, products or services, and to be applied by designers, companies and other social sectors. The model was so named because people/humans are the start point of the process, and are present in all the stages, as it considers that products and services are designed for people.

The IDEO HCD process⁵ has three different phases: the inspiration phase, the ideation – or creation – phase, and the implementation phase. Each of them are divided into various tasks.

The first task in the inspiration phase involves the creation of a project plan, by fixing a timeline, framing the design challenge, defining the strengths of the company, and identifying what the team will need to come up with innovative solutions for.

The second task concerns building a team: an interdisciplinary mix of professionals with a broad range of expertise and the ability to think in an abstract way to ideate new things.

The third task is about recruiting tools. In this phase, the team starts defining the target group by defining multiple variables, such as: age, gender, social class, lifestyles, linked consumer insights, etc. All this information gives the team valuable feedback to start addressing the challenges of the project.

The fourth task is focused on defining the challenge or the problem to solve.

The fifth task is to carry out research following various methodologies: interviews, immersions, observations, guided tours, collages, analogous inspirations, etc., in order to understand the hopes, desires and aspirations of the target. Based on the results of the research, the audience may even be re-defined.

Once the inspiration phase has finished, then the ideation phase begins. In this phase the design team has to create a strong, well-defined creative brief that

⁴ <https://www.ideo.com/post/design-kit>

⁵ IDEO, 2015, The Field Guide to Human-Centered Design

should be understandable by other team members (managers, marketing experts, etc.)

The first task of the ideation (or creation) phase is to summarise all the findings of the previous phase, creating personas, defining the design principles, etc. The information is shared with the other team members to identify opportunities for the design techniques to apply, techniques such as: sharing inspiration stories, prioritising findings, creating insight statements, creating frameworks to visualise patterns and understanding other people's perspectives, etc.

Another task considered in this stage is to create an important number of ideas with brainstorming sessions, co-creation sessions, bundle ideas, mash-ups, etc. Subsequently, the best solutions are selected (e.g., by analysing their economic and technical feasibility, their level of desirability, developing business models, etc.).

In the ideation phase, some of the proposed ideas become more visible and tangible, through storyboards and prototypes. The first versions of the prototypes are tested by the target audience in order to get feedback. Having considered their opinions, the prototypes evolve and the product improves with each new version.

The last phase of IDEO'S process is implementation, in which the prototypes developed in the previous task are tested in real world conditions, by carrying out a pilot test in the market where it is going to be launched, in the scenarios where it is going to be distributed and used, etc.

Important tasks that need to be approached in this phase are: defining a roadmap and strategies, detecting and contacting key partners, engineering (cost analysis, resource assessment), building work teams to carry out all the necessary tasks to produce the product and launch it on the market.

Furthermore, in this phase, the company tests the product, monitors and evaluates the data to communicate the results to the stakeholders and iterate the process by beginning with the inspiration phase again, if necessary.

Design Council

The double diamond diagram was created by the Design Council in 2005 to represent the design process. Composed by four phases, Discover, Define, Develop and Deliver, it maps the divergent and convergent stages of the design process, showing the different modes of thinking that designers use⁶ (Figure 9)

⁶ Council, D. (2007). A study of the design process. UK Des. Council, 44, 1-144.

Figure 9. Design Council's design process.

Discover is the first quarter of the double diamond model marks the start of the project. This begins with an initial idea or inspiration, often sourced from a discovery phase in which user needs are identified.

Define is the second quarter of the double diamond model represents the definition stage, in which interpretation and alignment of these needs to business objectives is achieved.

Develop is the third quarter marks a period of development where design-led solutions are developed, iterated and tested within the company.

Deliver is the final quarter of the double diamond model represents the delivery stage, where the resulting product or service is finalised and launched in the relevant market.

3.3 KEY ACTIVITIES IN NEW PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT

3.3.1 Initial approach

The design and manufacturing processes of wood, plastic, additives, resins, metal, textile, and paper and cardboard were analysed by an examination of secondary sources. The result of this study was a list of the main activities carried out by a toy company during both the design and manufacturing processes (Table 1). These activities are divided into three main phases according to their timing. They are: pre-production, production, and post-production. Pre-production refers to all the activities carried out before production begins. Production refers to all the activities carried out during the production of a product. Post-production refers to all the activities carried out once the production stage has ended. They should be understood as a first approach, which was validated in the questionnaire pilot test.

Table 1. List of hypothetical activities in a toy company.

1	Pre-production
1.1	Briefing – strategic definition, project generation
1.2	Idea generation and concept definition
1.3	Product design
1.4	Prototype development
1.5	Quality
1.6	User test
1.7	Marketing content development
1.8	Product engineering
1.9	Cost analysis
1.10	Price strategy
1.11	Product presentation – internal and external
1.12	Forecast – estimation of number of units to produce
1.13	Mould development
2	Production
2.1	Supplier management
2.2	Raw materials and components buying
2.3	Half-finishing manufacturing
2.4	Assembly
2.5	Safety experts – certification and laboratory
2.6	Storage
3	Post-production
3.1	Transport and logistic
3.2	Product placement – product placement in the store
3.3	Advertisement – publicity, media planner
3.4	Shop assistance
3.5	User assistance
3.6	Sales analysis – market evolution
3.7	User feedback

3.3.2 Pre-production stage

The manufacturing activities that companies most commonly carry out internally are: price strategy, cost analysis, product presentation and briefing definition. On the other hand, the manufacturing activities companies most frequently outsource are: mould development, prototype development, user test and product engineering (Figure 10).

Analysing the number of companies that evaluated the various manufacturing activities as being a very important or key aspect, the most important activities for the toy companies are: cost analysis, product design, price strategy, quality control, idea generation and briefing (Figure 11).

Figure 10. Manufacturing activities in pre-production stage.

Figure 11. Manufacturing activities importance in pre-production stage.

3.3.3 Production stage

The manufacturing activities that companies most commonly carry out internally are: supplier management, storage, raw materials and component buying and assembly (Figure 12). On the other hand, the manufacturing activities companies most frequently outsource are: safety certification and laboratory, half-finishing manufacturing and assembly (Figure 13).

Figure 12. Manufacturing activities in production stage.

Q. Please indicate which of the following activities are carried out and/or are outsourced by your company in the category selected (multiple choice)

Figure 13. Manufacturing activities importance in production stage.

Q. Please indicate the importance of the activities when developing new products in the category selected (important or key aspect)

Analysing the number of companies that evaluated the various manufacturing activities as being a very important or key aspect, the most important activities for the toy companies are: certification and laboratory, raw materials and components buying, half-finishing manufacturing, supplier management and assembly. The manufacturing activity evaluated as a very important or key aspect by the least number of companies is storage.

3.3.4 Post-production stage

The manufacturing activities that companies most commonly carry out internally are: sales analysis, user feedback and user assistance (Figure 14). On the other hand, the manufacturing activities companies most frequently outsource are: transport and logistics, advertising and product placement (Figure 15).

Figure 14. Manufacturing activities in post-production stage.

Q. Please indicate which of the following activities are carried out and/or are outsourced by your company in the category selected (multiple choice)

Figure 15. Manufacturing activities importance in post-production stage.

Q. Please indicate the importance of the activities when developing new products in the category selected

Analysing the number of companies that evaluated the various manufacturing activities as being a very important or key aspect, the most important activities for the toy companies are: market evolution (sales analysis), transport and logistic, user feedback and user assistance. The manufacturing activity evaluated as a very important or key aspect by the least number of companies are: shop assistance, product placement and advertising.

3.3.5 New toy development process definition

Based on the results of the personal interviews carried out for this project, AIJU's experts defined a new toy development procedure. This model is composed of 6 different phases: immersion, conceptual design, detailed design, production, delivery and evaluation that can be applied during all the previously mentioned phases. Each of the above mentioned phases is composed of a number of activities showed in Table 2.

Table 2. Toy phases and activities.

TOY PHASES	TOY ACTIVITIES
IMMERSION Strategy Definition	
Empathise	Market & design research
Define	Briefing
	Price strategy
	Project development and management
CONCEPTUAL DESIGN	
	Idea generation and concept definition
	Prototype development
	Marketing and content development
DETAILED DESIGN	
	Product engineering
	Mould development
PRODUCTION	
Pre-production	Supplier management
	Raw materials and components buying
	Manufacture of pre-series
	Forecast
Production	Manufacture of production
	Assembly
	Half finishing manufacturing
	Quality control
DELIVERY	
Storage	Storage
Distribution	Transport and logistics (from manufacturing warehouses to toy shops)
Sales	Product placement
	Advertising
	Shop assistance
EVALUATION*	
Desirability	User appeal and suitability
Viability	Sales analysis
	Cost analysis
Feasibility	Safety certification

*Internal presentation

*External presentation -presentation to clients

In order to validate the model created by AIJU's experts, the new toy definition process was compared with previous literature (for more information please consult point 3.2.1. of this report). The result of this analysis supported the validity of the process and the definition of the process was accepted. The main difference found was that the Stanford model does not give a detailed explanation of the activities related to the production and delivery of the product (Table 3).

Table 3. Toy phases and different process stages comparison.

TOY PHASES	DESIGN COUNCIL	IDEO SOCIAL	STANDFORD
IMMERSION	DISCOVER	INSPIRATION	EMPATHISE
Empathise	DEFINE		DEFINE
Define	DEVELOP	IDEATION	IDEATE
CONCEPTUAL DESIGN		IMPLEMENTATION	PROTOTYPE
DETAILED DESIGN			
PRODUCTION	DELIVER		
Pre-production			
Production			
DELIVER			
Storage			
Distribution			
Sales			
EVALUATION (Applied to all phases)			TEST
Viability			
Feasibility			
Desirability			

4 TECHNOLOGIES AND TECHNIQUES IN THE TOY SECTOR

4.1 MOST FREQUENT EXISTING PROCESSES AND TECHNIQUES TODAY

The toy manufacturing system has remained constant at a certain level in recent years, with injection processing being the most used technique. Despite this, some companies are incorporating new technologies into their processes⁷.

In order to obtain information on the most frequent existing processes and techniques in toy manufacturing today, toy companies were asked about which manufacturing processes and finishing processes their companies used regarding each material used.

4.1.1 Materials used in the toy sector

The materials analysed were: plastics, additives and/or resins; wood and derivatives; metal; textile; paper and cardboard; and electric and electronic components. The results showed that plastics, additives and resins were the material most used in the toy sector. Paper and cardboard was also an important material, followed by metal and electric and electronic components. On the other hand, wood (and derivatives) and textiles are the materials with least presence in the toy industry (Figure 16).

Figure 16. Most used materials in toy manufacturing.

Most used materials in toy manufacturing

Q. Please indicate the activity you perform in your company when producing the products in this category regarding the materials used (not including packaging) (multiple choice)

Regarding material transformation, the most common activity for toy companies is: "stock and distribution the final product", followed by "definition of the

⁷ Asunción Martínez (2003). Nuevas tecnologías en la fabricación de juguetes. Departamento de Ingeniería de Producto y Ensayos de AIJU. Interempresas.net Recovered from: <http://www.interempresas.net/Plastico/Articulos/7189-Nuevas-tecnologias-en-la-fabricacion-de-juguetes.html>

specifications and others transform the raw materials”, and “assembly of half-finished products”. Only one company indicated that they produced the raw material (Figure 17).

Figure 17. Most common activities regarding the material transformation.

Q. Please indicate the activity you perform in your company when producing the products in this category regarding the materials used (not including packaging) (multiple choice)

4.1.2 Plastic, additive and/or resin transformation

The most frequent processes toy companies use to transform plastics, additives and/or resins are: injection moulding, blow moulding, thermoforming, machining, additive manufacturing and extrusion. In all cases, the number of companies that outsource this process is higher than those that perform it internally (Figure 18).

Regarding the finishing processes of these types of materials, painting, cutting, deburring, machining/ milling are the most frequent processes used by toy companies. Once again, these processes are outsourced by high number of companies (Figure 19).

Figure 18. Most frequent manufacturing processes in plastics, additives and/or resins.

Figure 19. Most frequent finishing processes in plastics, additives and/or resins.

Most frequent manufacturing processes in plastics, additives and/or resins

(n=37)

SOURCE: AIJU 2017

Q. Please indicate the manufacturing process used in your company regarding plastics, additives and/or resins

Most frequent finishing processes in plastics, additives and/or resins

(n=37)

SOURCE: AIJU 2017

Q. Please indicate the finishing processes used in your company regarding plastics, additives and/or resins

Regarding when companies last invested in these manufacturing processes, some information may be significant: 12 of 43 toy companies have invested in injection moulding in the last five years, 2 toy companies did so between six and ten years ago, and only one did so more than ten years ago. These results serve to highlight that this manufacturing process is still quite strategic and companies still invest in, acquire or improve the injection moulding machines. Concerning blow moulding, 5 companies invested in this technology more than ten years ago, whereas 3 companies did so in the last five years. The responding companies have not invested in thermoforming in over ten years.

4.1.3 Wood and derivatives transformation

The most frequent processes toy companies use to transform wood and derivatives are: drilling, sheet metal cutting, edge banding, and sawing. In all cases, the number of companies that outsource this process is higher than those that perform it internally (Figure 20).

Regarding the finishing processes of these types of materials, varnishing, sanding and cleaning operations are the processes toy companies use most frequently. Again, these processes are outsourced by a high number of companies (Figure 21).

Figure 20. Most frequent manufacturing processes in wood and derivatives.

Q. Please indicate the manufacturing processes used in your company regarding wood and derivatives

Figure 21. Most frequent finishing processes in wood and derivatives.

Q. Please indicate the finishing processes used in your company regarding wood and derivatives

4.1.4 Metal transformation

The most frequent processes toy companies use to transform metal are: machining, conformation and punching, in all these cases the number of companies which outsourced this process is higher than the ones which do it internally (Figure 22).

Regarding finishing processes of these types of materials, polishing, surface treatments, galvanising, electrolytic coatings, chemical and electrochemical are the processes toy companies use most frequently. Once again, these processes are outsourced by high number of companies (Figure 23).

Figure 22. Most frequent manufacturing processes in metal.

Figure 23. Most frequent finishing processes in metal.

Q. Please indicate the manufacturing processes used in your company regarding metal

Q. Please indicate the finishing processes used in your company regarding metal

4.1.5 Textile transformation

The most frequent processes toy companies use to transform textiles are: sewing, die cutting and tailoring. In all cases, the number of companies that outsource this process is higher than those that perform it internally, except tailoring (Figure 24).

Regarding the finishing processes of these types of materials, the processes toy companies use most frequently are: printing, stuffing filling, dyeing and stamping. In most cases, toy companies outsource these types of processes (Figure 25).

Figure 24. Most frequent manufacturing processes in textiles.

Q. Please indicate the manufacturing processes used in your company regarding textiles

Figure 25. Most frequent finishing processes in textiles.

Q. Please indicate the finishing processes used in your company regarding textiles

4.1.6 Paper and cardboard transformation

The most frequent processes toy companies use to transform paper and cardboard are: cutting, pressing, drying and calendering. In all cases, the number of companies that outsource this process is higher than those that perform it internally (Figure 26).

Regarding the finishing processes of these types of materials, the processes toy companies use most frequently are: folding, varnishing and perforating. Once again, these processes are outsourced by high number of companies (Figure 27).

Figure 26. Most frequent manufacturing processes in paper and cardboard.

Most frequent manufacturing processes in paper and cardboard

(n=26)

SOURCE: AIJU 2017

■ INSIDE THE COMPANY
■ OUTSOURCED

Q. Please indicate the manufacturing processes used in your company regarding paper and cardboard

Figure 27. Most frequent finishing processes in paper and cardboard.

Most frequent finishing processes in paper and cardboard

(n=26)

SOURCE: AIJU 2017

■ INSIDE THE COMPANY
■ OUTSOURCED

Q. Please indicate the finishing processes used in your company regarding paper and cardboard

4.1.7 Electric and electronic components

Regarding electric and electronic components, toy companies usually buy these components. None of the companies that answered the electronic questionnaire manufactured electric and electronic components (Figure 28).

Figure 28. Activities regarding electric and electronic components.

4.2 EMERGING PROCESSES AND TECHNIQUES IN MANUFACTURING

In order to obtain information on emerging processes and techniques in toy manufacturing, toy companies were asked about which technologies they were considering acquiring. Table 4 shows the list of manufacturing processes proposed by respondents in order to select the next acquisition for the company.

Table 4. List of manufacturing processes proposed for next acquisition

3D printing	Precision milling
3D scanning	Sandblasting (cleaning, polishing)
Acrylic bending machine	Sewing machine
Circuit production	Soldering station
CNC milling	Thermostatic basin
Drone	Transfer press

Furnace	Vacuum forming
Hot string	Vinyl cutting
Knitting machine	Virtual reality
Laser cutter	Welding machine
Lathing	
Pottery wheel infrared oven	

The results in Figure 29 indicate that a large number of toy companies were not considering any purchase and a few did not share this information. Those toy companies that were considering acquiring new technologies, were mainly interested in 3D printing. On the other hand, 3 companies were focused on buying sewing machines. Regarding this technology, the high participation of the doll industry justified this result.

Figure 29. Future purchases of technologies by toy companies.

Future purchases of technologies

(n=43)

SOURCE: AIJU 2017

Q. Is your company considering buying any of these technologies in the near future? (multiple choice)

4.3 LEADING-EDGE PROCESSES AND TECHNIQUES IN MANUFACTURING

Concerning this section, respondents were asked, according to their experience, what manufacturing technology trends could drive the toy industry in the next five years.

Several of them agree with the potential of 3D printing in the toy sector. This activity could be carried out as an internal process during the creation phase, mainly during prototyping. Another possibility that respondents indicated was based on the end user. They envisioned users having a 3D printer at home, which could make it possible for toys to be printed and assembled by the children themselves. On the other hand, augmented reality, virtual reality and drones were considered as new technologies that will be present in future toys.

Another scenario considered is the implementation of robots, with the aim of helping with finishing processes – such as painting or pad printing – or in final assembly. This fact would entail a change in the duties and abilities of workers.

5 CONCLUSIONS AND FURTHER WORK

Finding #1 PRODUCTION OUTSOURCED

In analysing section 4 of the results of this report it can be concluded that the majority of manufacturing processes involved in manufacturing toys in Europe and transforming materials are performed by an outsourced company, instead of by the company itself, in-house.

This fact means that European toy companies are more focused on the conceptual design, detailed design production, and the delivery phases than on the production phase. They are more “commercial” than “industrial” companies.

Finding #2 INDUSTRIAL RELOCATION

The location of toy manufacturing processes has experienced great changes in the last few decades (Table 5). During the 90s, all the activities carried out by European toy companies concerning the creation of a new product were located in their own country.

At the beginning of the new century, some European companies started to outsource the processes related to manufacture to Asian countries, whilst maintaining the activities related to design, marketing and engineering in Europe.

This process is changing continuously, and in recent years it can be observed that some companies have been outsourcing the processes related to engineering to Asian countries, taking advantage of the proximity of two areas that are directly connected.

Table 5. Evolution of manufacturing processes location.

DECADE	DESIGN	INGENIERING	MANUFACTURE	MARKETING
1990	EUROPE	EUROPE	EUROPE	EUROPE
2000	EUROPE	EUROPE	ASIA	EUROPE
2010	EUROPE	ASIA	ASIA	EUROPE
2020	?	?	?	?

The evolution of this process for the coming decades is certainly unpredictable. Some experts suggest that a technological revolution and an increase in transport costs (e.g., by adding a pollution tax) could reverse the process and manufacturing could return to European countries. On the other hand, some experts suggest that there is a considerable possibility that design activities will be outsourced to Asia in coming years.

Finding #3 IMMERSION, DISCOVER, INSPIRATION, EMPATHISE, DEFINE

An important difference found in this project, when comparing the process of creation of a new toy between big companies and SMEs, is the time and resources assigned to the immersion phase.

In the literature we have looked at, the immersion phase is named the 'discover', 'inspiration', 'empathise', or 'define' phase. It does not matter how is named, what is important is the fact that this activity should be performed by SMEs, but a large number of them do not do so. This fact implies that small companies very often begin the activity of generating ideas with an inadequate level of information and knowledge about markets, consumer insights and trends.

This problem is related with the function assigned to the marketing department in most of the toy companies, which is often focused only on sales and not on user analysis. In other words, toys marketing departments should provide the necessary information (immersion phase) to toy designers before the generation of new ideas, and not be limited to adding their value once the products have been designed.

Finding #4 INNOVATION BARRIERS

One of the main barriers for innovation in the toy industry is the absence of historical data for this type of products in a sector where the clients and forecast responsible based most of their decision in this type of data.

Finding #5 COMPANIES PROFILE

Based on the Toy Industries of Europe association (2017⁸), the toy industry is composed of 5,000 companies, with sales of €16.5 billion in 2015. Obviously, there are significant differences between companies. Table 6 shows the main variables that define a toy company profile.

Table 6. Companies profile.

VARIABLE	COMPANY PROFILE	DESCRIPTION
Manufacturing processes	Industrial	An industrial company is the type of company that carries out all the manufacturing process internally
	Commercial	This type of company is related with the outsourcing of manufacturing processes to Asia and/ or other countries, one of the major changes in the toy industry in the last decade. Commercial companies usually focus all their

⁸ <https://www.toyindustries.eu/>

VARIABLE	COMPANY PROFILE	DESCRIPTION
		efforts on design and marketing processes and they usually outsource manufacturing
Turnover	Micro and Small	Small and micro companies have a turnover of less than 10 million, and less than 50 employees. A special type of company in this group are Start-ups
	Medium and Large	Medium and large companies have a turnover of more than 10 million, and more than 50 employees
Core activity	Manufacturers	The main activity of this type of company is to design, engineering and sometimes produce the toys.
	Distributors	In the last few decades, distributors have increased the number of products they sell that are their own brand. Usually, this type of company buys finished toys, but there are some examples of distributors that also undertake the design stage, e.g., Imaginarium.
Internationalisation process	Local	This type of company sell most of their toys in their own country
	Global	This type of company sells its toys in different countries and continents. Normally, this type of company has offices in different parts of the world.
Value proposition	Physical products	This type of company focuses its activity on the creation of new toys
	Content generators	These companies have evolved from a toy company to a media company: TV series and films are a core activity for them, engaging children and then making money by selling toys
Toy value	Educational	All toys have an educational value, but for these companies this variable is the main reason for creating a new toy. They sell toys to families and also to schools/ teachers, usually through educational channels. These companies named its products as specialty toys.
	Commercial	Usually this type of toy is made for enjoyment and entertainment. Even if they have educational

VARIABLE	COMPANY PROFILE	DESCRIPTION
		value, the focus is centred on fun. These companies named its products as toys
Toy technology	High level of technology	Technology has had a great influence on the toy industry in recent decades, and some companies see technology as their main strategy of differentiation, by adding technology to their products when the technology is mature, and its price range is reasonable for a toy. Clear examples of this type of toys are: robots, electronic pets, drones, etc.
	Low level of technology	This type of company normally does not add technology to their products because they do not have the knowhow or resources required, or because they believe that children are overwhelmed with technology.

PART B: TOYLAB FRAMEWORK

6 COLLABORATIVE DEVELOPMENT APPROACHES IN THE MANUFACTURING SECTOR

6.1 INTRODUCTION

The present section includes state-of-play analysis and comparative benchmarking of alternative collaborative development platforms identified during our research. Before the different approaches concerning this subject are presented, it is important to declare what product development includes, as considered in the framework of the project.

According to Entrepreneur⁹ product development is “*The overall process of strategy, organisation, concept generation, product and marketing plan creation and evaluation, and commercialisation of a new product*”.

Alternative definitions are more detailed such as the following provided by TechTarget¹⁰:

“Product development, also called new product management, is a series of steps that includes the conceptualization, design, development and marketing of newly created or newly rebranded goods or services. The objective of product development is to cultivate, maintain and increase a company's market share by satisfying a consumer demand.”,

or more general, like the one found in the Business Dictionary¹¹:

“The creation of products with new or different characteristics that offer new or additional benefits to the customer. Product development may involve modification of an existing product or its presentation, or formulation of an entirely new product that satisfies a newly defined customer want or market niche”.

Interestingly enough, the latter definition is not ideal under the scope of our research since it doesn't describe the different stages included in product development, consequently presenting it like a one-and-done procedure. Nevertheless, that is not the case. ToyLab partners consider that the former two definitions describe what product development represents for the (Toy) Manufacturing sector, while they are fully in line with the relevant literature studied.

⁹ <https://www.entrepreneur.com/encyclopedia/product-development>

¹⁰ <http://searchcio.techtarget.com/definition/product-development-or-new-product-development-NPD>

¹¹ <http://www.businessdictionary.com/definition/product-development.html>

The next term to be declared refers to ‘collaborative product development’. Gülçin Büyüközkan & Jbid Arsenyan (2012. Collaborative product development: a literature overview) provide a review of product development processes and collaborative product development as an emerging way of doing business. Building on top of older definitions for collaborative product development, the authors consider this as “a technology-centered process including two or more partners with diverse competence, experience, culture, skill and location joining complementary resources to design/develop new/innovative/improved products in order to gain competitive advantage, innovate, explore new markets, share risks and costs and accelerate PD process.” (Büyüközkan, Arsenyan 2012). The visualisation of this definition is shown in following Figure 30, from which the different phases of product development will be drawn and explained.

Figure 30. Collaborative Product Development Process (Büyüközkan, Arsenyan 2012).

Having clarified the concepts of product development and collaborative product development respectively, as considered in ToyLabs, a state of the play analysis has been performed. In the pursuit to be exhaustive, it was decided that research should be divided into two parts: academic journals derived from scientific papers and commercial platforms identified through desk research. In order to better cite the reviewed approaches, a “collaboration platform” reporting schema is developed and applied. A set of appropriate criteria/ features relevant to other collaboration platforms are identified and described below:

- Paper Title: encompassing all the basic information for the mentioned papers such as title and URL.
- Platform name: if the paper includes the development of a collaboration platform, the name is mentioned here. Nevertheless, most papers propose frameworks that do not end up as platforms. When that is the

case, the name of the framework is mentioned in this column with the word "framework" in parentheses for better clarity.

- Available features/ modules: among the different features or individual modules that a collaborative platform may have, four of them, as presented next, are considered the most significant for ToyLabs. Consequently, it is of great importance to check for the existence of any of these features in the frameworks/platforms we review so that we can later conclude on the advantages that each of them offers in a collaboration manufacturing platform. If the framework/platform under study mentions the use of one or more of these components, then it is mentioned in the respective field. Brief descriptions of the features examined are provided next:
 - Analytics: analytics is used to discover patterns from data, relevant to market trends or existing products of the company. What it basically does is collect specific data and interpret them into useful conclusions that can assist the company in solving problems and optimise procedures such as designing a new product or forming a better commercialisation strategy. Under the scope of the ToyLabs project, the main focus is placed on three different types of analytics; social, market and enterprise analytics. The main difference between the three is the source from where they collect data. Specifically, **social analytics** collects data from stakeholder conversations in various online places and social media. **Enterprise analytics** "refer to the process of having data, business and process analytical capabilities across an enterprise. It provides organizations with the ability to collect analyze and process analytical data in all or most functions of the business."¹²
 - Partner matching: when talking about collaborative manufacturing platforms, it becomes obvious that the platform's stakeholders need a tool to help them find and connect with other stakeholders they can potentially cooperate with. A partner matching module provides partner search and matching services intended for enterprise collaboration. The search component allows the filtering of results based on the criteria set and the background and expertise of the available partners, as stored in the corresponding repository. In the case of manufacturing industries these criteria can include cost, skills, production

¹² <https://www.techopedia.com/definition/30592/enterprise-analytics>

capacity, materials used, estimated delivery time, geographical location etc.

- Augmented/Virtual reality: augmented reality "is the integration of digital information with the user's environment in real time. Unlike virtual reality, which creates a totally artificial environment, augmented reality uses the existing environment and overlays new information on top of it."¹³ AR/ VR modules can be used in collaborative manufacturing at the design phase to bring together designers with end users and other potential stakeholders, in order to provide better visualisations of new designs and get more accurate feedback from the participating community. More information about the use of AR/VR in manufacturing will be relayed in a following chapter.
- User feedback: in collaborative manufacturing environments information and feedback is conveyed through many different channels. Therefore, a feedback management service is required to distribute information in various channels, as well as collect and analyse feedback from those channels and actively engage in conversations.
- Experimentation
 - Application area: utilised to indicate the application area of the reported approach. Based on the research conducted and the platforms that were actually found, it makes sense to divide the application area in three categories that will be described below. It needs to be mentioned that a platform can offer tools that make it relevant to more than one category.
 - Collaborative Product Development Platforms: this category includes all the platforms that contain infrastructure and technologies that can help at one or more stages of the collaborative product development process. In other words, these platforms enable manufacturing resource distribution and sharing for remote collaboration. Design, development and marketing of a new or improved product are the main stages, and the practitioners can consider these three stages as the main collaboration areas. (Büyüközkan, Arsenyan 2012). Design and development tools may include augmented/virtual reality modules that allow multiple designers in geographically distributed areas to

¹³ <http://whatis.techtarget.com/definition/augmented-reality-AR>

collaborate in the design of a new product. Moreover, they may include infrastructure for data gathering and sharing that can help identify current procedures and approaches in a specific domain.

- **Partner Matching Platforms:** Partner identification, partnership formation and partnership management are identified as the three main stages of the partnership process. (Büyüközkan, Arsenyan 2012). Platforms that belong in this category provide tools that can perform all three stages of the partnership process. Partner identification is performed by filtering certain criteria that the user ideally wants his partner to fulfil. For example, if a manufacturing company wants to find a partner that can construct a prototype of a design, the results might be filtered according to price, materials used and available technologies. The second part, partnership formation, refers to the negotiation process and the paperwork and agreements that the two partners will have to exchange in order to make their partnership official. That means that the developer of a partner matching platform must have knowledge of the relevant procedures in partnership formation in the domain of his application. Finally, partnership management refers to the tools that allow partners to ensure the success of their collaboration by managing the governance of strategic objectives and expert knowledge (Hipkin, Naudé 2006)
 - **Manufacturing Management and Orchestration Platforms:** The final category includes platforms that can help manufacturing companies manage their procedures, automate their manufacturing processes and improve communications inside the company. For example, an orchestration platform may include tools relevant to order management, inventory management, accounting and customer relationship management.
- **Target groups:** if the paper under study indicates a specific target group that is aimed to take advantage of the paper's results, it will be mentioned here. Possible values can be SMEs, Companies, Factories, Organisations etc.
 - **Lifecycle phases:** the phases of the ToyLabs Toy Development Process are mentioned above. If the paper under study indicates

that the framework/ platform is used in one or more of these phases, they will be mentioned here.

- Co-design participants: this field will not have a value unless the framework/ platform under question has a Co-design component. If it does, then the stakeholders that participate in the design of the product along with the original company's designers will be mentioned here. Possible values include end-users, external consultants, organisations etc.
- Benefits: this field will contain qualitative benefits drawn from the framework/platform under question. Possible values of this field can be improved communications, better resource distribution and sharing etc. In other words, this field contains descriptive benefits and should not be confused with Key Performance Indicators.
- Key Performance Indicators (KPIs): KPIs indicate the effectiveness of the platform/ framework under question in handling a specific activity. In manufacturing, KPIs may include performance, quality, cost and time. If the results of the paper affect any KPI in a positive way, then it will be mentioned here.

Having explained all the values used in the "collaboration platform" reporting schema mapping of the different approaches/frameworks/platforms retrieved from bibliographic research in various sources, the following tables (Table 7 & Table 8) present the most important works (in research and commercial level respectively) in a brief and easily comparable way.

Table 7. Research Works.

Paper Title	Platform Name	Available Features				Experimentation					Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)
		Analytics	Partner Matching	AR/VR	User Feedback	Application Area	Target Groups	Lifecycle Phases	Co-design participants	Benefits	
Cloud manufacturing service platform for small- and medium-sized enterprises https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s00170-012-4255-4	BISTOP	Yes (enterprise, market) ¹⁴	Yes	No	Yes ¹⁵	Collaborative Product Development, Partner Matching, Manufacturing Management and Orchestration	SMEs	Production	NA	Enables manufacturing resource distribution and sharing. Provides centralised management. Guarantees service efficiency and quality. Widely praised by users.	Provides reliable, high-quality, low-price manufacturing service Setup time is drastically decreased
Design, programming and orchestration of heterogeneous manufacturing systems through VR-powered remote collaboration http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0736584514000738	VirCA	Yes ¹⁶ (market) ¹⁷	Yes ¹⁸	Yes	Yes ¹⁹	Collaborative Product Development, Partner Matching, Manufacturing Management and Orchestration	Remote laboratories, industries, universities	Ideation, Design, Development	End-Users, Researchers, Developers, Engineers	Enables sharing manufacturing equipment for remote collaboration. Allows for increasingly sophisticated bidirectional data exchange between VirCA and third-party physical devices. Allows flexible interconnection of virtual test production lines, allowing for thorough testing.	Improves efficiency in a cost-effective manner. High availability of the platform. Supports plug-and-play paradigm which provides extensibility and versatility. Reduces training time of new employees

¹⁴ For some service resources, it can form the systematic information tools to aggregate the domain knowledge.

¹⁵ Users evaluate the cooperator, and form the users' credit files in which the cooperation information can be searched and checked by users

¹⁶ VirCA provides a high-level information pool in which information relevant to the system's state can be collected, maintained and possibly predicted

¹⁷ a possible list of entities (taken from the context of industrial robotics) that can connect to the VirCA pool

¹⁸ The matchmaking between requests and capabilities is performed by an inference engine, on demand.

¹⁹ CogInfoCom channels have been tested and validated in VirCA, as well as applied to VirCA and VirCA-like systems to support auditory feedback on tactile percepts [66] and auditory feedback in virtual sketching applications [68]

Paper Title	Platform Name	Available Features				Experimentation					Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)
		Analytics	Partner Matching	AR/VR	User Feedback	Application Area	Target Groups	Lifecycle Phases	Co-design participants	Benefits	
An interoperable solution for Cloud manufacturing http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0736584513000069	ICMS	Yes (enterprise) ²⁰	Yes	No	Yes ²¹	Collaborative Product Development, Partner Matching, Manufacturing Management and Orchestration	SMEs, Manufacturing Enterprises	Design, Development, Production	Customer Users, Enterprise Users	Traverses all the possible paths and finds the most sufficient solution in terms of time. Makes it possible to realise remote collaboration, coordination, and interaction among participants. Provides data interoperability, customised service and better enterprise performance.	Setup time is drastically decreased. The actual material cost is drastically reduced. The cost of IT infrastructure is cut down via reduced management and maintenance effort. More manufacturing objects can be achieved with minimum additional investment and effort. The plug-and-play ability of service applications enables flexibility and adaptability
A collaborative and integrated platform to support distributed manufacturing system using a service-oriented approach based on cloud computing paradigm	XMLAYMOD	Yes (Enterprise, Market) ²²	No	Yes	No	Collaborative Product Development, Manufacturing Management and Orchestration	Manufacturing Enterprises	Design, Development, Production	NA	Through the use of XML it enables collaboration among different CAX agents in a distributed enterprise.	Reduces manufacturing costs and expands capacity. Capability to use new modules: base for the reduction of high cost and time to improve the platform. Efficiently extendable. Ensures data safety through the use of XML Security service.

²⁰ According to the request document, BA searches in the MRsource database for potential solutions. Afterward an initial ST file is created and sent back to the user.

²¹ After the feedback/evaluation document is finished by the user, the CMService is terminated

²² In recent researches, creation of a product information model to enable collaborative design and manufacture among distributed enterprises has been found as an essential paradigm [49]; [50]; [51]; [52]. The integration based on this data model helps the enterprises to achieve digital manufacturing and computer integrated manufacturing paradigm to increase their competitiveness and abilities to respond to market demands that its trends changes in an acceptable time [46]; [53]; [54].

Paper Title	Platform Name	Available Features				Experimentation					Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)
		Analytics	Partner Matching	AR/VR	User Feedback	Application Area	Target Groups	Lifecycle Phases	Co-design participants	Benefits	
http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0736584512000932											
A Web-Based Platform for Collaborative Product Design, Review and Evaluation https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007%2F978-1-84996-172-1_3#page-1	CPD	Yes (enterprise) ²³	Yes	Yes	Yes ²⁴	Collaborative Product Development, Partner Matching	SMEs, Manufacturing Industries	Design, Development	Designers, Engineers, managers, Suppliers, Customers	Provides a variety of functionalities for real-time collaboration during design activities. Online interactive review for evaluation purposes. Has flexible, modular architecture, easy to be used and extended. Can be used for a wide range of products. Consequently it is an appropriate tool for SMEs that cannot afford sophisticated tools.	Applicable to a wide range of products. Easy to use and extend. Cost-effective. Increases productivity of engineering teams. Considerably decreases time required to complete the design phase.
Development of a web-based collaboration platform for manufacturing product and process design evaluation using virtual reality techniques	DiCoDEv	No	No	Yes	Yes ⁱ	Collaborative Product Development	Manufacturing Industries	Ideation, Design, Development	End-users, Designers, Manufacturers,	Allows multiple users to work in a collaborative way. Leads to more efficient evaluation of a design using digital human simulation. Provides quick and easy product data storage and decision support for evaluating alternative designs.	Considerably decreases time required to design the product. Improves team productivity.

²³ Quick and easy product data storage and sharing through an easy to use web-based content management platform

²⁴ The decision support tool that supports the evaluation of the alternative design solutions, based on a set of criteria, and decision making

Paper Title	Platform Name	Available Features				Experimentation					Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)
		Analytics	Partner Matching	AR/VR	User Feedback	Application Area	Target Groups	Lifecycle Phases	Co-design participants	Benefits	
http://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/09511920600690426											
A Conceptual Framework for Collaborative Design and Operations of Manufacturing Work Systems http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0007850607601395	ADMS (framework)	Yes (Enterprise)	No	No	No	Collaborative Product Development, Manufacturing Management and Orchestration	SMEs, Manufacturing Companies	Ideation, Design, Development, Production	End-users, Customers	Provides a framework that supports geographically distributed operations in manufacturing. The platform provides a powerful information system for management, control and maintenance	Improves visibility and control of the processes. Provides operations support by various services to ensure product quality, high productivity, reliability and system availability
An Internet-based Collaborative Platform for Managing Manufacturing Knowledge http://cordis.europa.eu/docs/projects/contract/2/284602/080/reports/001-Finalbrochurefinal.pdf	Know4Car	Yes (market)	No	Yes	No	Collaborative Product Development, Manufacturing Management and Orchestration	Manufacturing Companies	Includes the whole cycle	NA	Organises process knowledge so that it is more efficiently managed, Agent-based Engineering allows engineers to plan and simulate possible solutions. Supports efficient collaboration between organisations. Includes training options that aim at improving the performance of engineering teams	Faster process design. Reduced time-to-market along with the associated costs. Reduced time for identifying relevant knowledge
A Knowledge Based Collaborative Platform for the Design and Deployment of		Yes (market)	No	Yes	No	Collaborative Product Development, Manufacturing Management and Orchestration	Manufacturing Companies	Development	NA	Boosts collaborative processes such as project management and data exchange.	

Paper Title	Platform Name	Available Features				Experimentation					Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)
		Analytics	Partner Matching	AR/VR	User Feedback	Application Area	Target Groups	Lifecycle Phases	Co-design participants	Benefits	
Manufacturing Systems https://hal.inria.fr/hal-01461852/document											
An Innovative Framework Supporting SME Networks for Complex Product Manufacturing https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/file/index/docid/1055991/filename/pro24.pdf	Net-Challenge (framework)	No	Yes	No	No	Collaborative Product Development, Partner Matching, Manufacturing Management and Orchestration	SMEs, Manufacturing Companies	Design, Development, Production	Designers of cooperating companies	Allows SMEs to create dynamic collaboration networks for complex product manufacturing while also taking advantage of more market opportunities. Provides decision support tools to improve the company's management processes.	Information about potential collaborators is more reliable and accurate. Less time to perform partner selection.
Collaborative Product Development and Customization: A Platform-Based Strategy and Implementation https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Ram_Sriram2/publication/228736757_Collaborative_Product_Development_and_Customization_A_Platform-	WEBCDM C	No	No	Yes	No	Collaborative Product Development	Manufacturing Companies	Design, Development	Designers of cooperating companies, Customers, Manufacturing Engineers	Designers in different teams and organisations may participate and collaborate in the design process (Zha, Sriram 2004). Provides chat functions so that designers can communicate with each other during the design process.	Reduced effort and time for product

Paper Title	Platform Name	Available Features				Experimentation					Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)
		Analytics	Partner Matching	AR/VR	User Feedback	Application Area	Target Groups	Lifecycle Phases	Co-design participants	Benefits	
Based Strategy and Implementation											
INFELT STEP: An integrated and interoperable platform for collaborative CAD/CAPP/CAM/ CNC machining systems based on STEP standard http://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/0951192X.2010.527373	INFELT STEP	No	No	Yes	No	Collaborative Product Development, Manufacturing Management and Orchestration	Manufacturing Companies	Design, Development, Production	Designers of cooperating companies	One of the major operations of the INFELT STEP platform is its ability to storage operations(Valilai, Houshmand 2010). Allows designers to cooperate each using a different CAD program. Allows integration of product data based on the STEP standard	Reduces time to market
Toward a cloud-based manufacturing execution system for distributed manufacturing http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0166361514000311	NetMES	Yes (enterprise)	No	No	No	Manufacturing Management and Orchestration	Manufacturing Companies, SMEs	Development, Production	NA	Supports distributed manufacturing. Web-based system that requires no installation. Supports the decision making process and simplifies the business processes(Helo et al. 2014).	Offers better control of production quality by improving the defect detecting process. Thus overall system performance is improved and costly downtime is avoided
TOWARDS A CLOUD-BASED DESIGN AND MANUFACTURING PARADIGM:	CBDM (framework)	Yes (enterprise, market, social)	No	Yes	No	Collaborative Product Development, Manufacturing Management and Orchestration	Manufacturing Companies, SMEs	Ideation, Design, Development, Production	Customers, Designers, Managers	Enables collaboration in distributed manufacturing environments. Improves customer and product management. Offers	Reduces time and effort required for the design phase. Reduces time-to-market. Increases innovation rate.

Paper Title	Platform Name	Available Features				Experimentation					Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)
		Analytics	Partner Matching	AR/VR	User Feedback	Application Area	Target Groups	Lifecycle Phases	Co-design participants	Benefits	
LOOKING BACKWARD, LOOKING FORWARD http://proceedings.asmedigitalcollection.asme.org/proceeding.aspx?articleid=1736119										capability of intelligent search for design and manufacturing solutions enabled by semantic web technology and social network analysis, thereby promoting information and knowledge reuse and cost reduction(Wu et al. Sunday 2012).	

Table 8. Commercial Works.

Company Site	Platform Name	Available Features				Experimentation					Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)
		Analytics	Partner Matching	AR/VR	User Feedback	Application Area	Target Groups	Lifecycle Phases	Co-design participants	Benefits	
http://3discovered.com/	3Discovered	Yes (market)	Yes	Yes	No	Collaborative Product Development, Partner Matching	Manufacturing managers, designers, engineers	Includes the whole cycle	End-Users, designers	Allows users to design, customise, manufacture and deliver objects anywhere in the world. Gives access to the latest 3D technologies without costly hardware investments. Provides analytics and partner matching for designers.	Lowers costs for manufacturing managers by providing them with the required expertise and technologies.
https://www.exact.com/	Exact	Yes (social, market)	No	No	No	Manufacturing Management and Orchestration	Manufacturing Companies	Development, Production	NA	Helps manage your manufacturing company. Automates manufacturing processes. Improves	Saves time in calculating quotes.

Company Site	Platform Name	Available Features				Experimentation					Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)	
		Analytics	Partner Matching	AR/VR	User Feedback	Application Area	Target Groups	Lifecycle Phases	Co-design participants	Benefits		
											communications inside the company.	
http://www.happyworker.com	Happy Worker	No	No	Yes	Yes	Collaborative Product Development	Global teams, smaller firms, end-users	Includes the whole cycle	End-users, designers	Pays especial attention to the clients' needs and wants. Guides clients through the toy making process. Provides a lot of prototyping techniques (3D printing, moulding, casting etc.)Includes third-part inspections for quality control. Handles shipment all across the globe.	NA	
https://www.mfg.com	MFG.com	No	Yes	No	No	Partner Matching	Procurement professionals, Engineers	Development, Production	NA	Performs partner matching between manufacturing professionals with CNC machining companies, Injection moulding companies, Metal Stamping companies etc.	Reduces component costs, Shortens lead times, Protects intellectual property, Decreases supplier risk	
https://www.xometry.com	Xometry	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Collaborative Product Development	Manufacturing Companies, Engineers, CAD users,	Includes the whole cycle	Customers	Provides an efficient way to manufacture custom parts with techniques including 3D printing, CNC Machining, Casting etc. Provides customers with the capability to upload 3D models and get instant quotes about cost, materials and manufacturing techniques. Enables co-design between the company's designers and the customers.	Low prices, Fast lead times, High Quality, Easy-to-use Platform, Applicable in many fields of manufacturing	

Company Site	Platform Name	Available Features				Experimentation					Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)
		Analytics	Partner Matching	AR/VR	User Feedback	Application Area	Target Groups	Lifecycle Phases	Co-design participants	Benefits	
http://sourceeasy.com/	Sourceeasy	No	No	No	Yes	Collaborative Product Development	Apparel Manufacturing Companies, SMEs	Includes the whole cycle	Customers	Provides services for the whole cycle of apparel production from design to production and delivery, thus saving companies the trouble of dealing with freelancers.	Significantly cuts cost and lead time
http://www.thomasnet.com/	Thomasnet	Yes (market)	Yes	No	No	Partner Matching	Manufacturing Companies	Development	NA	Provides product search capabilities and downloadable CAD models. Capability to search only for suppliers certified to quality standards. Enables suppliers to promote their business	Over 700.000 industrial and commercial suppliers. Over 60.000 quality certified suppliers
https://macrofab.com/	Macrofab	No	No	No	No	Collaborative Product Development, Manufacturing Management and Orchestration	Hardware Companies	Development, Production	NA	Provides an integrated platform that leads to more efficient prototyping. Helps with the management of many manufacturing and business procedures. Provides multiple shipping options.	Lowers costs and lead times. No shipping fees from manufacturing to inventory.

6.2 SELECTED COLLABORATIVE DEVELOPMENT PLATFORMS

Even though the literature is not brimming over successful applications of collaborative development platforms in manufacturing, since most of the approaches do not reach the practical level, it was managed with a more thorough search to detect a few successful examples of collaborative platforms both from scientific sources and commercial platforms.

BISTOP: an application prototype of SME-CMfgSP

The need: Deal with the problems faced by SMEs in the manufacturing sector such as the lack of technology and communication channels which diminish a company's international market ability.

The solution: A new framework was developed named SME-CMfgSP (SME-oriented cloud manufacturing service platform) based on emerging technologies such as Cloud Computing, Internet of Things (IoT) and agent based technologies for information sharing. Based on this framework a platform named BISTOP was developed, funded by the Chinese Ministry of Science and Technology and developed by Beijing N-Dimensions Cooperation Technology Co., Ltd (NDtech). The main purpose of the platform is to perform partner matching between manufacturers and clients while also providing real time reports on the production process so that the client can participate in the production.

Results: After launch, with the “customisation, improvement and growing” service mode, BISTOP online management service has been accepted, applied, and praised widely by users. At present, BISTOP has been designated to be a professional service cooperation partner by many government departments in China. (Huang et al. 2013)

VirCA: Virtual Collaboration Arena

The need: Solve the problems that arise from modern manufacturing systems which are composed of different stakeholders and participants as well as highly-customised components. These components are sometimes located in different geographical locations thus creating problems in orchestrating and optimising the manufacturing procedures.

The solution: The authors were led to the conclusion that virtual reality collaboration systems are an ideal solution to tackle the above mentioned problems. In this context the VirCA platform was developed to act as a communication medium among different stakeholders through the use of virtual/augmented reality. Moreover, the platform includes tools for the management of manufacturing procedures. Finally, the platform is based in a plug-and-play paradigm meaning that it can connect with systems and applications of manufacturing companies, making it efficiently extendable.

Results: The implementation of VirCA in three pilot applications, showed its benefits in actual manufacturing environments. Specifically, it enabled stakeholders to share manufacturing equipment for real time remote collaboration and improved efficiency while cutting costs. Additionally, the platform was used for education purposes, mainly for training new employees of manufacturing companies, effectively reducing the training time. Finally, "VirCA allows for the flexible inter-connection of virtual test production lines, allowing for thorough testing, readjustment and process innovation activities even in cases where a real life separation of such activities from the physical production line would be inhibitive costly" (Galambos et al. 2015).

ICMS: Interoperable Cloud-based Manufacturing System

The need: Extend the concept of cloud manufacturing by dealing with the more common problems in this area, specifically "implementing manufacturing-related software in Computing. Unlike software programme and IT infrastructure, physical machines, monitors, and facilities cannot be readily deployed on the Cloud. There is also a need to understand the intermediate processes from raw material to finished products." (Vincent Wang, Xu 2013)

The solution: In order to take advantage of emerging state-of-the-art approaches, relevant to cloud manufacturing the ICMS platform was developed to enable remote collaboration and interaction among stakeholders in a collaborative manufacturing environment. The platform includes features such as databases that contain knowledge about products and procedures, a partner matching module to handle requests from users who are searching for a provider for a particular service and a smart cloud manager capable of supporting manufacturing procedures.

Results: Two case studies were developed to evaluate the benefits of the ICMS approach. It was proven that the platform helped manufacturers reduce the costs of materials and IT infrastructure needed while also decreasing setup time. Overall, it provided seamless collaboration between participants, data interoperability, customised service and better enterprise performance.

XMLAYMOD

The need: Solve the problems of modern day manufacturing businesses that struggle to find effective solutions that offer remote collaboration and data integration. A successful solution concerning manufacturing data integrity is the use of the ISO 10303 (STEP) standard. However past works have shown that using STEP can weaken both integration and collaboration capabilities.

The solution: To deal with the problems arising from the use of the step standard, the authors applied the use of XML data structures in an older version of the platform named LAYMOD.

The XML structure was used to provide required services for distributed collaboration manufacturing, while taking advantage of a new feature of the STEP standard which makes it possible to work with an XML data structure.

Results: The resulting platform enables data integration while the CAx agents collaborate in the distributed manufacturing environment. The benefits also include reduced manufacturing costs and expanded capacity while the use of XML Security Service ensures data safety (Valilai, Houshmand 2013).

CPD: Collaborative Prototype Designer

The need: Today, product development is the result of a network-based collaborative process, because most of the projects require co-operation among geographically distributed expert groups with diverse competence.²⁵ Despite the investment made in the recent years, both in research and in industrial applications, the global market still lacks integrated, flexible, and cost-effective solutions to support the collaborative product design (Mavrikios et al. 2011).

The solution: In this context the CPD system was developed to serve as a multiuser real-time collaboration tool for distributed and collaborative product development activities, focusing on SMEs that cannot afford such sophisticated tools. The system can be used by designers, engineers, managers, suppliers, and customers and it provides a variety of functionality for collaboration during design activities such as 3D visualisation environments, online reviews for evaluation purposes and partner matching.

Results: Through a case study and a testing phase that lasted approximately a year the benefits of the CPD were identified. Specifically, the collaboration functionality, the capability for multimode (CAD/VR/AR) visualisation, and the overall user friendliness of the web- and VR-based platform were considered to be the strongest points of the platform. Additionally, the participating companies reported that the platform shows big potential in reducing both the costs as well as the time required to complete the design phase.

DiCoDEv: Distributed Collaborative Design Evaluation

The need: Today's global business environment in the manufacturing industry is characterised by unprecedented competitive pressures and sophisticated customers, who demand innovative and speedy solutions. (Pappas et al. 2006) Thus, manufacturing companies need to innovate themselves frequently, both by designing new products and by enhancing the quality of the existing ones.²⁶

²⁵ Chryssolouris G (2006) Manufacturing systems: theory and practice, 2nd edn. Springer-Verlag, New York (ISBN: 978-0-387-25683-2)

²⁶ Chryssolouris, G., Manufacturing Systems: Theory and Practice, 2nd edition. 2005 (Springer-Verlag: New York)

Consequently, the scope of this work was to provide a real-time collaboration platform for manufacturing purposes that can service the whole cycle of a manufacturing process.

The solution: In this context the DiCoDEV platform was developed that enables multiple users to collaboratively work in the same project in real time. The innovation concept of this platform lies in the use of virtual reality (VR) technology for the development of the working display environment that provides also navigation, immersion and interaction capabilities for all collaborative users in real time (Pappas et al. 2006).

Results: The resulting platform provides a number of benefits which were also evaluated through a pilot application. Specifically, the benefits of the platform include multi-user visualisation, immersion and interaction, the ability to maintain and review alternative designs, while also decreasing time to complete the design phase and improving team productivity.

ADMS: Adaptive Distributed Manufacturing System (framework)

The need: There is a steady growing pressure on companies, urged by the worldwide competition, to streamline operations involving product and product related manufacturing system design, product manufacturing and system maintenance. (Sluga et al. 2005) Furthermore, manufacturing companies today cannot hope to survive by themselves and need to continually build upon their relationships with both their customers and their suppliers.

The solution: The ADMS framework (based on the concept of Complex adaptive manufacturing systems (CAMS)) was developed to support geographically distributed operations in manufacturing. Moreover, it provides a powerful information system for management, control and maintenance.

Results: In order to evaluate the framework's usefulness, it was used in a case study which included an industrial network in the die-casting industry, dealing with issues that arose from communication problems. The framework's implementation provided a number of benefits such as improved communication, data management and control of the manufacturing processes.

6.3 AUGMENTED REALITY APPLICATION IN COLLABORATIVE DESIGN

In the current highly competitive business environment, the manufacturing industry is facing constant challenges of producing innovative products at reduced time-to-market. The increasing trend of globalised manufacturing environments

requires real-time information exchanges between the various nodes in a product development life cycle, e.g., design, setup planning, production scheduling, machining, assembly, etc., as well as seamless task collaboration among these nodes. Product development processes are becoming increasingly more complex as products become more versatile and intricate, and inherently complicated, and as product variations multiply with the trend of mass customisation. Manufacturing processes have to be more systematic in order to be efficient and economically competitive. (Ong et al. 2008)

Moreover, the evaluation of a product involves a demonstration of the designer's work and the visualisation should demonstrate that the design fits spatially and aesthetically into its environment. (Ahlers et al. 1995) This process of product design evaluation is important to get feedback from the user's perception in different fields such as functional, aesthetical or usability and to make sure that the product characteristics meet the user needs. In this context, augmented reality can be used as a powerful tool in the hands of designers to acquire the early feedback they need to come up with truly novel design that respond to the expectations of the manufacturer. The application of Augmented Reality (AR) can reduce cost and time and also improve the quality of product evaluations integrating the context elements and a more natural interaction with virtual elements. (Ye et al. 2007)

AR is a novel human-computer interaction tools that overlays computer-generated information on the real world environment. This novel technique can be combined with human abilities to provide efficient and complementary tools to assist manufacturing tasks. AR has already been demonstrated to be a solution in many applications, both in manufacturing and other fields. Several successful demonstrations have been made in the medical domain, military training, tele-robotics, entertainment, maintenance, and manufacturing.⁹ During the state of the art research it was discovered that many collaborative approaches include an augmented reality component mainly during the design phase, in both hands on and feedback based co-design. This proves that AR, as a technology, has not only matured enough for commercial use over the last years, but can also prove to be an innovative and effective solution in solving a lot of the aforementioned problems encountered in modern day manufacturing.

Figure 31. AR technology.

The challenge is to design and implement integrated AR-assisted manufacturing systems that could enhance the manufacturing processes, as well as product and process development, leading to shorter lead-time, reduced cost and improved quality. In the next part, platforms (drawn both from commercial systems and scientific papers) that include such augmented reality tools for product development, will be presented, emphasising on the added value that the augmented reality module offer. Platforms drawn from scientific publications will be mentioned first followed by commercial platforms that implement augmented reality systems.

VirCA (Péter Galambos et al 2015) is a platform that gives users the capability of sharing manufacturing equipment for collaboration and orchestration of manufacturing processes involving multiple machines. In that scope, augmented reality is used as a communication medium for testing and training of complex manufacturing systems. Specific tasks that take advantage of augmented reality include production line design and testing, technical education and industrial training.

XMLAYMOD (Valilai, Omid Fatahi; Houshmand, Mahmoud 2013) is a platform able to support distributed manufacturing collaboration and data integration based on the STEP standard. The XMLAYMOD platform uses augmented reality mainly in the design phase. What is noteworthy is that the final product is separated into multiple components and each of them is designed with the help of the AR module. The 3D data of each component are then sent to the manufacturing agents that can handle the product's assembly and production processes.

CPD (Canetta, Redaelli et al. 2011) was developed to support the collaborative product design activities. With the help of virtual reality tools the users have the ability to join collaborative CAD sessions where the product is designed cooperatively (although each user works on his own desktop). After building the geometry models of the product the users can design the prototype. They are able

to navigate, visualise, and interact with the virtual prototype, so as to review the different design solutions. Following the evaluation of the product the prototype is stored in an online repository where users can review all the products available in a 3D interactive environment.

DiCoDEv (Pappas, M.; Karabatsou, V.; Mavrikios, D.; Chryssolouris, G. 2006) is a platform that provides real-time collaboration of multiple users, mainly for process and product design evaluation during every stage of a product's development cycle. This is achieved by integrating a virtual project environment in the platform, where users are able to create or modify 3D designs while working on the same environment. The virtual reality tool offers many benefits to users such as improved collaboration and team productivity while also decreasing the time required to design the product.

Know4Car (funded by EU (Grant 284602), under FP7 Factories of the Future (FoF) theme FoF-ICT-2011.7.4) is a platform that attempts to make collaboration and knowledge management more effective throughout the product lifecycle. In the scope of the project, augmented reality tools are integrated in the platform to provide faster training to operators and technicians of manufacturing companies.

Moving on to the commercial platforms, the best case of augmented reality application is seen in 3Discovered which allows users to design, customise, manufacture and deliver objects anywhere in the world. The platform offers clients use of 3D design tools in order to create or customise digital designs which can then be published to online repositories. On the other hand, Xometry doesn't include an augmented reality tool but the services it offers depends on users uploading their 3D models in the platforms repository. After the model is uploaded, the platform provides feedback on pricing, lead times and the best processes to manufacture the client's design. Finally, HappyWorker is a company that creates customised toys but their services do not include an online platform. Nevertheless, the company's information clearly mentions that CAD tools and 3D modelling are used during the prototype phase in order to receive the client's feedback

7 MARKET AND DESIGN RESEARCH METHODOLOGIES

7.1 CUSTOMER EXPECTATIONS

7.1.1 Introduction

One of the most important factors to consider when developing a new product or service is the current and future characteristics of consumers; their values, needs, desires, behaviours, etc. This section presents specific protocols and methodologies focused on understanding customer expectations.

It is relevant to bear in mind that the toy industry has various customers: children, parents and relatives. All of them should be studied from different perspectives to get the right information that could really assist companies.

7.1.2 Who carries out research on customer expectations

Marketing agencies

Most marketing agencies carry out research on customer expectations. Some of the most globally important agencies are:

- Nielsen "What People Watch, Listen to and Buy" (www.nielsen.com)
- GfK "Market research and user experience research experts" (www.gfk.com)
- Ipsos "Global market and opinion research specialists" (www.ipsos.com)
- Toluna "Real-time consumer insights, automated survey solutions" (www.toluna-group.com)
- TNS Global market research company (www.tnsglobal.com)

Internal research in companies

In many cases, large companies also carry out some internal research. Frequently these studies focus on obtaining information about the acceptance of a product that is being developed, which is tested before going any further with the design, or with a specific marketing strategy.

Two of the most important companies in the toy industry, Mattel and Hasbro, have facilities to carry out this type of research. Fisher Price, now owned by Mattel, has had the PlayLab for over 50 years. It was the first facility of its kind in the industry: a research area to observe children testing toys during the development

process. The reason for this is because they want to see children's reactions first-hand. Figure 32 shows a published results of a design developed by Fisher Price with the information collected in their PlayLab.

Figure 32. Published results of a design developed by Fisher Price.

Hasbro also has the FunLab where the company develops its in-house toy and game testing. As they indicate on their website; "The purpose of the FunLab is to enable Hasbro's researchers, designers, marketing professionals and engineers to observe children's reaction to different toy/game concepts as well as a first-hand look at play habits".

7.1.3 Customer's expectations research methodologies

There are a variety of data analysis and research tools to figure out people's attitudes and behaviours, and anticipate changes in customer expectations. These tools come from the social science, business, design and technology fields. Some of them overlap in scope to a certain extent, sometimes being complementary. Although the lines are blurred, it is important to clarify that the kind of insight that each one provides is very different.

To study the user and its market, a combination of market research and design research can work properly to develop a project from a holistic perspective.

Market research is primarily about understanding what people will buy. It uses both qualitative and quantitative methods, but the ultimate goal is always to understand what people want to buy. On the other hand, design research is not about markets, trends, what people say they will buy, their demographics, or how the market can be segmented and analysed. Rather, design research looks at what a person feels about using a product or service. It's not about looking at trends that capture generalisations. It's about looking at very specific, deep-dive information about users²⁷.

Innovation guided by design has come to complement the market's view that, in order to innovate, one must focus on the development or integration of new technologies and on opening and/or servicing new markets. Besides these technological and marketing factors, the Design Thinking consultancy innovates primarily by endowing products, services or relationships with new meanings²⁸.

Human-centred design methodology has been defined by several companies and experts such as IDEO, Stanford or the Design Council, but the common point in all of them is a creative approach to problem solving that is focused on people rather than demographics.

Human-centred design consists of three phases. In the Inspiration Phase you'll learn directly from the people you're designing for as you immerse yourself in their lives and come to deeply understand their needs. In the Ideation Phase you'll make sense of what you learned, identify opportunities for design, and prototype possible solutions. And in the Implementation Phase you'll bring your solution to life, and eventually, to market. And you'll know that your solution will be a success because you've kept the very people you're looking to serve at the heart of the process²⁹.

In this section, some common and relevant methodologies are described in order to determine how research can be conducted with users.

²⁷ Lahiri Chavan, A. UX Research and Market Research. 2012. Human Factors International

²⁸ Vianna, M. (et. al) Design Thinking Business Innovation. 2013. MJV Press.

²⁹ IDEO. Design Kit. Recovered from: <http://www.designkit.org/human-centered-design>

7.1.3.1 *Qualitative research*

Focus Group

A group of people (usually 4 to 6) are questioned about their opinions and perceptions towards a concept, product, service, or advertisement. Other feedback such as insights into product usage, or purchase habits (where and why they would buy the product) can also be obtained through this method.

Personal interviews

Are one-to-one conversations in which questions are asked to get specific answers. This allows researchers to get information about people who are geographically far away from the interviewer. Interviews are usually face-to-face but new technologies are broadening the possibilities and they can be done with videoconferencing. The cost of the webcam-based interviews, compared to having to travel to where customers are, is helping this way of interviewing to become more common.

Ethnographic Research

There are various methods related to ethnography (the study of people and cultures) that can give the researcher lots of relevant information about customer expectations. Some of the techniques most commonly used by companies and agencies are the following:

- *Immersive research techniques* allow researchers to capture behaviours, emotions and cognitive perceptions of individuals in context at the moment where the individual experiences them (Macdonald, E., Wilson, H). In general, the method requires that researcher immerse him or herself into the daily life and environment of the person or group studied. There are different variations of this methodology. Some examples used in the research community are:
- *A day in the life*: Following a person or a family during a whole day from waking up to going to bed to register their daily routines or to see niches in the market where problems are presented and there are no products to solve them (Figure 33).

Figure 33. AIJU's research board a day in the life of two babies.

- *In-Home*: A researcher gets together with children and/or parents to talk, play or test prototypes in a natural environment.
- *Shop-along*: Accompany a person or a family in a shopping experience.

7.1.3.2 Quantitative Research

Online interviews

This is the most common method used to get quantitative data today. The interviewee is sent a link to a questionnaire that can be accessed through a computer, tablet or even a smartphone. With this method the company making the interview obtains the information directly in the form of a spread sheet that can be easily converted into graphics. With the fast-pace of this method there has been an increase in micro-surveys; interviews with a small amount of questions (2-3).

Social media analytic tools

There is a variety of software available to analyse data about what is being done and said in social media. Information posters can be related to a company, to a product or a strategy.

Wearables-based research

Wearables can collect an important amount of quantitative data in a passive manner. For instance, smart fitness devices are able to report on daily activities, heart rates, sleep patterns, and so on. Smart watches can give information on location and Web browsing data, or even TV viewing habits.

7.1.3.3 Both qualitative and quantitative research

Facial analysis and Eye tracking

With modern technologies the researcher can register and analyse the movements of the eyes, to understand what first captures the attention of a consumer. As people are not really aware of some important factors that define their preferences, with this method the researcher can collect data beyond what the subject says.

In a similar way, with facial analysis technology it is possible to track and measure consumers' unbiased behaviour responses and interest in something in a non-intrusive way (Figure 34).

Figure 34. Example of results on facial analysis technology³⁰.

Neuromarketing

Neuromarketing is a way to study the brain's responses to products, marketing campaigns, etc., by using medical technologies such as functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging (fMRI).

Visual artificial environments

Virtual and augmented reality are technologies that are also being used to understand human behaviour as they present a product or immerse the person in a specific surrounding, almost as if the product or the environment was real.

7.1.4 AIJU's protocol to study customer expectations

³⁰ Photography from <http://sightcorp.com/portfolio/market-research/>

AIJU's research on consumer expectations is a combination of knowledge between market research and design research, always taking into account the user and the market.

The AIJU department in charge of this type of activities is called Children's Research, and its expertise is centred on detecting new opportunities, creating and improve products, services, spaces and systems in relation with children and their environment. The department has specific infrastructures, materials and protocols that allow it to carry out this type of service for companies.

7.1.4.1 *Infrastructure and materials*

AIJU has two Living Labs at the service of companies. The objective of a Living Labs is to observe the behaviour of users in a controlled environment but which in turn resemble as much as possible the real situations of use and purchase of products. For this, the specialists in children recreate different types of environments and situations (purchase, use, etc.) depending on the objectives of the study. This type of study collects information about the tastes, needs and requirements of the users in all the phases of creation of a new product or service.

The Play Lab is located at the AIJU headquarters in Ibi while the Child Lab is located at the office in Valencia. The Child Lab is a hidden viewing room for the observation of users in play sessions. It is equipped with a two-way mirror and CCTV.

PlayLab

This is a children's play area for the investigation and study of toys with a surface area of 300 m², equipped with CCTV (Figure 35).

Figure 35. AIJU's PlayLab.

ChildLab

It is equipped with a two-way mirror, and CCTV, giving the possibility of viewing the interviews made in real time from the offices of the company itself (streaming), technologies of analysis of emotional response, simulation of sales line, etc. The infrastructure of the room is divided into two parts: the room where users stay and the observation room. The first room is multipurpose, which adapts according to the needs of the study and participating users. It can accommodate between six and eight adults or children. The furniture and decoration is interchangeable and adapts to the type of user (for example, with different sizes of tables and chairs). In addition, it has a flip chart, projector and linear sales shelves (Figure 36).

Figure 36. AIJU's ChildLab.

The observation room is isolated by mirrored glass where researchers and companies can directly observe the behaviour of the guests. The installation allows the dynamics to be recorded as the room is equipped with a remote control video camera and microphones. In addition, it is possible to carry out detailed visualisations in real-time thanks to the powerful zoom system of the installed cameras (Figure 37).

Figure 37. ChildLab observation room.

7.1.4.2 *Recruitment*

The participants in these studies come from AIJU's database. This database is a collection of data on people interested in participating in studies that AIJU carries out for companies and for regional, national or international projects.

AIJU's database is made up of heterogeneous profiles, such as: children from 0 to 16 years old, parents and future parents, educators and teachers, playcentre caregivers, disability experts, paediatricians, psychologist, sociologists, children's development experts, people who love play, etc. Likewise, various institutions collaborate, such as ONCE (Organización Nacional de Ciegos Españoles), CEAPAT (Centro de Referencia Estatal de Autonomía Personal y Ayudas Técnicas) or ASINDOWN (Asociación y Fundación Síndrome de Down de Valencia), among others.

AIJU's database is registered on the "Agencia de Protección de Datos". This institution is responsible for ensuring compliance with legislation on data protection and monitoring its implementation, especially in regard to the rights of information, access, rectification, opposition and cancellation of data (ARCO).

AIJU does not share the information gathered in the database. All data collected will remain anonymous and will only be linked with a family code, in order to ensure the safety and confidentiality of the respondents and their families.

The type of customer expectations studies that AIJU usually carries out with the database are focused on understanding the preferences and acceptance of concepts, ideas, products or prototypes. We also analyse children's patterns and behaviours in their play with toys and in the interaction with new technologies.

As said before, families in AIJU's database may participate in studies either face-to-face or remotely.

Face-to-face participation

Face-to-face participation can be conducted at AIJU's facilities:

- Childlab: a hidden viewing room for watching play or usability sessions with users.
- Playlab: a 300 m² children's playcentre with a two-way mirror for researching and studying children's behaviour in contact with toys or other children's products.

In addition, research can be conducted in collaborating schools and children's playcentres.

Remote participation

Remote participation can be conducted via telephone (e.g., survey), video conference (e.g., focus group) or by internet (e.g., online questionnaire).

7.1.4.3 Face-to-face studies at AIJU's facilities

The protocol followed to carry out face-to-face studies at AIJU's facilities is described below.

Figure 38. AIJU's face-to-face study protocol.

1. Definition of the sample

The sample is selected from AIJU's database depending on the objective of the study. The target is focused on families with children up to 14 years old who live in Spain.

A briefing describing the sample characteristics is sent to the person allowed to use the database. She or he applies filters in order to select the best sample that fits with the established requirements.

2. Recruitment of the sample

Communication of the study objectives. Contact with the sample defined is performed by the person allowed to use the database through a combination of email, landline telephone or mobile phone used specifically to contact with the families. The information given to families is about the type of methodology planned, the way to record the information generated (e.g., video recording, photos), the duration, the target needed (mother, father, child of specific age, etc.), the date and the place. If it is necessary to acquire extra knowledge about the consumption or preferences of the children or parents in order to select the sample, some questions to gather this information are included in the email or asked by phone.

Acceptation of participation. Families confirm participation or non-participation in the study by email or telephone (call or via WhatsApp). The person in charge of the recruitment accepts the participation, or not, depending on whether the target quota has already been reached.

The person in charge of the recruitment contacts more users (normally one or two more) than the study requires to ensure that the number of the sample to carry out the study is correct. If there is no absence, extra users convened also participate in the study, as long as this does not affect the methodology.

When carrying out the research in a school or playcentre, two authorisation letters are sent to them:

- A non-disclosure agreement for the director, in order to accept carrying out studies with children in the centre.
- An authorisation to parents in order to accept the participation of the children in the study and the recording. This authorisation is given to parents and, if they agree, it is returned signed.

Reminder. Once the sample has been selected, a reminder is made the day prior to the study by sending an email, a message via WhatsApp, or making a call. If there is a cancellation, the person in charge of the recruitment consults AIJU's family database in order to convene another user.

3. Participation of the users

Welcome and acceptance of participation in the study. This protocol differs depending on the user.

- Child participation: during the welcome and before starting the study, the mother, father or person responsible for the child is informed about the study and an authorisation to allow recording is given. The authorisation focuses on asking permission to take images of the child participating in the study and explains the way that the recordings will be used. Once the authorisation has been signed, the child can participate.
- Adult participation: Once the adult is in the room where the session is being recorded, the moderator explains that it is going to be recorded and asks for the consent of the participants. If there is someone that does not agree, she or he is free to withdraw from the study. Once all the participants have given their consent, the study starts.

Participation. In the case of children's participation, the study starts after parents, legal tutor or guardians have signed the authorisation and also if children have given their consent (depending on their stage of maturity). In the case of adults, the study starts after they have consented to the recording.

4. Compensation policy

In order to avoid the professionalisation of AIJU's family database, the compensatory item is a symbolic gift that AIJU gives as a sign of gratitude for participation. For this reason, AIJU's policy is to not reward participants with money, and offer gift cards as a last option.

When the study has finished, both child and adult participants are offered to select a toy from several options. If none of of them is desired, a gift card to spend in a toy shop or department store is offered.

5. Rest period

When a user has participated in a study, the date of participation is recorded in the database to calculate the next date when participation is possible. This measure is performed for several reasons:

- To allow as many people in AIJU's family database as possible to participate.
- To avoid the professionalisation of AIJU's family database:
 - People who are more interested in the gift than in altruistic participation.
 - People who know the methodology and technique well enough that may distort the opinions given.
- To ensure that the sample does not participate in a study with the same brand twice. This restriction is omitted if repeating with the sample is a company requirement.

For face-to-face studies, such as focus groups, the rest period given is two months.

7.1.4.4 Face-to-face studies outside AIJU's facilities

The protocol followed to carry out face-to-face studies outside AIJU's facilities (schools and children's playcentres) is described below.

Figure 39. AIJU's face-to-face outside Living Lab study protocol.

1. Definition of the sample

The sample is selected from AIJU's database depending on the objective of the study. The target is focused on schools and children's playcentres with children up to 14 years of age that live in Spain.

A briefing describing the sample characteristics is sent to the person allowed to use the database. She or he applies filters in order to select the best sample (i.e., schools and playcentres) that fits with the established requirements.

2. Recruitment of the sample

Communication of the study objectives. The contact with the sample defined is performed by the person allowed to use the database through a combination of email and landline telephone. The information sent to the school or playcentre contact is about the aim of the study, type of methodology planned, the way to record the information generated (e.g., video recording, photos), the duration, the target needed (mother, father, child of specific age, etc.) and a proposal of a date to carry out the study. In addition, AIJU describes the requirements for the study such as type of space, furniture, necessity of Wi-Fi, etc. If it is necessary to acquire extra knowledge about the consumption or preferences of the children or parents in order to select the sample, some questions to gather this information are included in the communication.

Acceptation of participation. Attached to the previous information, two authorisation letters are sent to the school or playcentre contacted:

- A non-disclosure agreement for the director, in order to accept carrying out studies with children in the centre.
- An authorisation to parents in order to accept the participation of the children in the study and the recording. This authorisation is given to parents and, if they agree, it is returned signed.

Reminder. Once the date is set, a reminder is made two days before the study by sending an email, a message via WhatsApp, or making a call. If there is a cancellation, the person in charge of the recruitment consults AIJU's database in order to convene another user.

3. Participation of the users

Acceptance of participation in the study.

- Child participation: If the parental authorisations have not already been gathered, this is done before starting the study. Once the authorisation has been signed, the children can participate.

- **Adult participation:** In the case that the study is intended for parents, before starting, the moderator explains the aim of the study and the way which the information is going to be collected (e.g., video, photos). The moderator asks for the consent of the participants. If the participant does not agree, she or he is free to withdraw from the study. When the participant has given their consent, and this has been recorded, the study starts.

Participation. In the case of child participation, the study starts after signing the authorisation, whereas with adults, the study starts after they have consented to the recording.

Compensation policy. In order to avoid the professionalisation of AIJU's family database, the compensatory item is a symbolic gift that AIJU gives as a sign of gratitude for participation. For this reason, AIJU's policy is to not reward participants with money and offer gift cards as a last option.

When the study has finished, there are two possibilities of reward depending on the centre policy:

- Centre receives the compensation. The centre receives the compensation (e.g., toys, school material, electronic devices, etc.) which is used in the centre by all the children.
- Participant receives the compensation. The participants are offered a selection of toys to choose from several options, or a gift card to spend in a toy shop or department store is offered. This situation is less common.

4. Rest period

When a centre has participated in a study, the date of participation is recorded in the database to calculate the next date when participation is possible. This measure is performed for several reasons:

- To allow as many people in AIJU's family database as possible to participate.
- To avoid the professionalisation of AIJU's family database:
 - People who are more interested in the gift than in altruistic participation.
 - People who know the methodology and technique well enough that may distort the opinions given.

- To ensure that the sample does not participate in a study with the same brand twice. This restriction is omitted if repeating with the sample is a company requirement.

For face-to-face studies, such as focus groups, the rest period given is two months.

7.1.4.5 Remote studies

The protocol followed to carry out remote studies (online questionnaires) is described below.

Figure 40. AIJU's remote study protocol.

1. Definition of the sample

The sample is selected from AIJU's database depending on the objective of the study. The target is focused on families with children up to 14 years of age that live in Spain.

A briefing describing the sample characteristics is sent to the person allowed to use the database. She or he applies filters in order to select the best sample that fits with the established requirements. An Excel file is generated and implemented on the questionnaire programme to send the questionnaire to the sample selected. If it is necessary to acquire extra knowledge about the consumption or preferences of the children or parents in order to select the sample, a filter question is included in the questionnaire.

A target quota is programmed in order to distribute the sample regarding to the study requirements. If one participant starts the questionnaire and the target quota has already been achieved, this is communicated to him or her and he or she is not permitted to complete the questionnaire.

2. Participation of the users (fieldwork)

Communication of participation. An email is sent to the families selected for the study. The body of the email has the following information:

- Aim of the study

- Link to the questionnaire
- Link to copy in the internet browser in case it does not work
- Link to communicate that the participant does not want to answer the questionnaire
- Link to unsubscribe

Acceptation of participation. Families confirm their participation or non-participation in the study by accepting the terms and conditions shown at the beginning of the questionnaire. A consent letter and an information letter are displayed.

- Consent letter: includes the name and aim of the project, participant request, estimated duration of the questionnaire, how the information will be transferred to third parties and information that the questionnaire is voluntary, among others.
- Information letter: includes the same information as the consent letter and potential benefits, possible risks, security, privacy and confidentiality issues and a contact with an AIJU technician, this link is accessible to the respondents throughout the whole study.

After having shown all this information, a button to accept the terms and conditions previously stated is included.

Reminder. After a set period (usually 5 days), a reminder is sent to the sample by email. The content of the email includes the aim of the questionnaire and a link to it. The reminder can be programmed to be sent according to the needs of the study.

Finalisation of the fieldwork. Once both the sample and the time is achieved, the questionnaire is closed. After this action, no one is able to answer it. Then, the technician starts the analysis of the data gathered.

3. Compensation policy

In order to avoid the professionalisation of AIJU's family database, the compensatory item is a symbolic gift that AIJU gives as a sign of gratitude for participation. For this reason, AIJU's policy is to not reward participants with money and offer gift cards as a last option.

When the questionnaire has finished, the system records the respondent participation and this information is included in AIJU's database in order to register the number of participations.

4. Rest period

When a respondent has participated in a questionnaire, the date of participation is recorded in the database to calculate the next date when participation is possible. This measure is performed for several reasons:

- To allow as many people in AIJU's family database as possible to participate.
- To avoid the professionalisation of AIJU's family database:
 - People who are more interested in the gift than in altruistic participation.
 - People who know the methodology and technique well enough that may distort the opinions given.
- To ensure that the sample does not participate in a study with the same brand twice. This restriction is omitted if repeating with the sample is a company requirement.

For remote studies, such as online questionnaires, the rest period given is one month.

7.1.4.6 Compensation policy

In order to avoid the professionalisation of AIJU's family database, the compensatory item is a symbolic gift that AIJU gives as a sign of gratitude for participation. For this reason, AIJU's policy is to not reward participants with money, and offer gift cards as a last option.

When the study has finished, both child and adult participants are offered to select a toy from several options. If none of of them is desired, a gift card to spend in a toy shop or department store is offered.

In studies in schools, when the study has finished, there are two possibilities of reward depending on the centre policy:

- Centre receives the compensation. The centre receives the compensation (e.g., toys, school material, electronic devices, etc.) which is used in the centre by all the children.
- Participant receives the compensation. The participants are offered a selection of toys to choose from several options, or a gift card to spend in a toy shop or department store is offered.

7.2 MARKET AND SOCIAL TRENDS

7.2.1 Introduction

Trends are the directions towards which something tends to move or change. Related to the market, trends give information about how a society and the industrial sectors are adapting to a great variety of variables that are in constant evolution. These changes define the behaviours of consumers and companies in aspects that are relevant to the development and distribution of products and services.

Detecting these changes, knowing their reasons and knowing what implications they will have for companies will prepare the industry to anticipate changes, adapt to them and even be able to generate them, appropriate them and boost them.

By identifying trends companies can detect variations in consumers' motivations, tastes and preferences before they become massive, with the intention of using this information to innovate and anticipate their strategies to have a competitive advantage.

To be able to determine the trends that are going to affect a specific industry it is necessary to study patterns and anomalies that are appearing and developing in society and can alert to deeper, stronger cultural transformations. These changes can occur in any field: architecture, vehicles, fashion, retail, art, design, science, technology, etc.

For instance, research shows that vehicles are tending towards being self-driven. This factor will influence the way children and their families interact and play in the car. That can be translated into specific opportunities for the toy and game industries.

To find out the most important and innovative trends that will affect the toy market in the near future, it is necessary to consider a broad range of factors. For that matter, to carry out a good trend research analysis it is relevant to have the collaboration of a large group of researchers from different disciplines.

It is also important to have experts in both national and international markets. Global trends have to be detected and interpreted, and then adapted to the local needs and characteristics of each industry.

The main goal of trend research is to provide companies with information that can assist them in creating and adapting their products and marketing strategies by considering the demands of consumers. Data also provides insights to define their target better by attending to attitudinal or lifestyle variables, transcending the classic segmentations by gender, age and social class.

7.2.2 Who carries out trend studies

There are various agents that carry out trend research for companies:

7.2.2.1 *Specialised agencies*

These are companies that are focused entirely on developing trend research and assisting companies with how to apply the information into their corporations. In order to be able to apply broad and global trends to company policy, it is necessary to adapt them to the characteristics and needs of each company and each project. These specialised agencies are experts on how to translate the trend into information that can really be applied in the specific context of a company.

They usually have coolhunters in different cities that collaborate with them, constantly sending them images and information on what is happening in the streets, in retail, and society in general.

Most of them present part of their results in events such as forums organised by fairs or other relevant conferences. They usually send newsletters with summaries of the data they are collecting to attract the attention of possible clients.

Some of the most relevant companies focused on trend research are the following:

- Future Concept Lab. Milan, Italy (<http://www.futureconceptlab.com/>)
- WGSN. North America, Europe, Asia, Latin America (www.wgsn.com)
- The Institute for The Future, California, USA (IFTF.org)
- Springwise, London, UK (www.springwise.com)
- Nelly Rodi. Paris, France (<http://nellyrodi.com/en>)
- Faith Popcorn. NY, USA (www.faithpopcorn.com/)
- Promostyl. Paris, France (www.promostyl.com/en/)
- Peclers. Paris, France (www.peclersparis.com)
- Psfk, Piers Fawkes. NY, USA (psfk.com)

Most of these consulting groups focus on analysing the behaviour of young people and the evolution of powerful brands in general. There are few specialised research consultants in the field of toys trends. Most consultancies are marketing research firms specialised in marketing to children in general. Some examples of these kinds of companies are listed below:

- Kidz Global. USA (www.kidzglobal.com)

- Smarty Pants, USA (<http://asksmartypants.com>)
- Kids Say, USA (<http://kidsay.com/>)
- Family kids and youth, UK (www.kidsandyouth.com/)
- Kids Industries the family agency (www.kidsindustries.com)
- Child Wise (www.childwise.co.uk)
- The Modern Kids & family. Spain (www.themodernkids.com)
- Griffiths Consulting (www.griffiths-consulting.de)

7.2.2.2 *Toy experts*

Individual professionals with extensive experience in the industry also sell their services to toy companies. Among them we find Stevanne Auerbach, known as Dr. Toy (<http://drtoy.com/>), Richard Gottlieb (www.globaltoyexperts.com/) or, Reyne Rice (<http://reynrice.com/>).

7.2.2.3 *Design consultancies*

Some of the most important design consultancies have a trend research department specialised in ethnography research and marketing. Design consultancies such as: IDEO, Smart design, Fjord, Frog design, P9 Design, Four23, The Stratos Group, Thrive, etc.

7.2.2.4 *Trend research department, internal to a company*

There are companies that have in-house experts. Some have a specific trend research department while others might have specialists working on trends from the marketing department. In general, companies create their own trend information for different reasons. One of the most important ones is that they can customise the trends to their particular needs and really get the information that is specific and relevant to their business. Moreover, they can always have access to updated information, data that no other company has access to. Most of the biggest companies carry out this kind of internal research (Philips, Microsoft, Nike, etc.). This is similar to what happens in the toy sector. The big corporations such as Mattel, Hasbro, Tomy, or Spinmaster have professionals and departments focused on carrying out their own trend studies.

7.2.2.5 *Toy Fairs*

In the last few years, trade fairs have also started to create and present information about trends. Both of the most important toy fairs in the world present

their own trends: Spielwaremesse (Nuremberg, Germany) and Toy Fair (New York, USA).

Spielwaremesse (Nuremberg, Germany)

With 2,871 companies exhibiting from 63 countries and 73,000 visitors from 123 nations in 2017, it is the biggest toy fair in Europe. Since 2014, the fair has provided information about the toy trends that can impact and influence the market each year.

For this purpose, the fair created a Trend Committee (Figure 41) with various international toy experts. One of them is Dr. Maria Costa, Director of children's Research at AIJU.

Figure 41. Spielwaremesse Trend Committee.

Figure 42. Trend Gallery, Spielwaremesse 2016.

An area of the fair, the Trend Gallery, is reserved specifically to promote their trends and show products related to them (Figure 42).

The trends from the Spielwaremesse Toy Fair are published on their official website. The trends from 2017 can be consulted at the following link:

<http://www.spielwaremesse.de/special/trendgallery-2017-en/?L=1>

Toy Fair (New York, USA)

Toy Fair (New York, USA) is a relevant fair for the sector, organised by TIA, The American Toy Industry Association. In 2017, it had 1,126 exhibitors from 31 nations and approximately 30,000 visitors (including nearly 13,000 retailers, wholesalers, importers, buying groups, and trade guests) from more than 100 countries.

Since 2013, the TIA has been presenting the trends, in different publications and media, that they consider will impact the market during the following months

after each fair. While this information is available to everybody, they also produce reports on different topics (emerging technologies, retail, etc.) that are available monthly only to TIA's members.

They publish the trend information on their website:

http://www.toyassociation.org/TIA/Industry_Facts/trends/IndustryFacts/Trends/Trends.aspx?hkey=d4a13ea2-d774-48ea-b4a3-4bfdbdd14a0f#.WM_MKPk1_cs

7.2.3 Trend research methodologies

To carry out trend research there are various requirements and methodologies that have to be considered. There are two main requirements that should be taken into account before starting to generate any trend research: a historical review with retrospective knowledge and a multidisciplinary team.

A historical review, retrospective knowledge. To envision the future, it is essential to know about the past. The history of the toy industry locally and internationally helps trend researchers understand the evolution of this sector and the reasons behind what happened. They cannot define what is new, innovative and trendy if they do not know the products that were on the market before and the strategies behind them.

In the same way, in order to comprehend the values and behaviours of new families, the researchers need to understand how they have changed through the centuries.

A multidisciplinary team. Determining trends, analysing them, characterising them, is complex work that involves consulting a wide variety of sources and experts. To define trends, it is necessary to review information from different areas and points of expertise. The team of trend researchers should be composed of experts in various fields related to marketing, sociology, anthropology, design, child psychology, engineering, etc. A multidisciplinary team with these kind of professionals study what is happening in the market and society from different perspectives, bringing a great range of information to trend meetings. It is relevant to have a coordinator that is actually a trend analyst, an expert that knows how to manage the wide variety of information to link it all together and determine specific trends.

Once the team has been created, with experts trained in the historical social and market facts that influenced the development of the industry, a work methodology should be selected. Some of the main methodologies that trend research teams are applying in their daily work are presented below:

Figure 43. Trend research protocol.

1. *Collect information*

To analyse market and social trends, a great amount of information from different sources should first be collected and organised. The methodology followed are desk research and observation, including visits to fairs, shops and influential cities.

Regarding desk research, there are various ways to gather the data. These are some of the main ones:

- News: daily review of news related to the evolution of the economy and the markets, the new technologies available, and the changes in society (demography, new habits, behaviour, values, etc.)
- Magazines: review of magazines specialising in families and children (e.g., Vogue Kids, Parents magazines, Crecer), or the industry (e.g., ToyNews, Juguetes B2B, Licencias actualidad, The Toy Book).
- Books: be updated with the new publications related to social changes, lifestyles, children's behaviour, new marketing strategies, design innovations, etc.
- Scientific research: review of papers based on the latest studies carried out in prestigious universities around the world. For instance, studies on how technologies affect children's development or their behaviour, and how we can create products to have a positive impact on their lives.
- Catalogues and websites from relevant companies and from distribution: follow up new products and the communication strategies of toy companies (Hasbro, Mattel, Playmobil, Lego, Chicco, Famosa, Haba, etc.), specialty stores (Learning Express, Imaginarium, Eureka Kids, etc.), and big distributors (Walmart, Target, Carrefour, El Corte Inglés, etc.)
- Social networks and other online resources: review of news, articles, and images posted on fair websites, blogs, and other social media platforms, such as Pinterest, Instagram, Facebook, etc.

There are general trend research blogs, such as Trendhunter and Trendwatching, that present ideas related to the children's industries. Other influential blogger trend experts also follow posts about parenting, toys and innovations: kidcrave.com, babyccinokids.com, tigriteando.com, www.ju-queteseideas.com, www.handmadecharlotte.com, www.pintandounama-ma.es, www.scrappingparados.com, kidsgiftsandtoys.com, etc.

Lately, many companies and distributors have started their own blogs as another platform to reach parents and children with tips about parenting as well as products they could buy (e.g. <http://blog.toysrus.co.uk/>, <http://blog-en.famosa.es/>)

The Spielwarenmesse, the toy fair in Nuremberg, Germany, also has an online blog/magazine where they publish weekly articles about different topics relevant to the industry (Figure 44).

Figure 44. Spielwarenmesse trend articles in their blog magazine.

Regarding observation, the most important activities are:

- Visits to fairs: Attending fairs related to toys, licensing, childcare, new technologies, education, art and design allow the trend team to gather current information about new product developments from a diverse range of companies.
- Distribution visits: Visiting both speciality stores and large retailers to analyse the products they are putting on the market and how.
- City visits: A great focus of innovation is concentrated on the big cities, and from there, little by little, trends spread towards rural areas. Trend

researchers travel and visit cosmopolitan cities such as New York, Chicago, Los Angeles, Paris, London, Barcelona, Berlin, Milan, among others.

2. Analysis and definition of trends

The analysis of so much information is confusing and can be misinterpreted, the trend specialists are trained to analyse and organise it in a way that can lead to conclusions. In this phase of the research, there will be multiple meetings with the multidisciplinary team. These sessions will be focused on looking for patterns that point towards specific directions.

After the trends have been determined, another relevant matter is to give them a name, usually a word that summarises the main ideas behind them.

3. Spreading the information

One of the most common ways to publish and spread the information is with trend books. These are usually sold through the same trend agencies that carried out the research or even via publishers and distributors specialising in this kind of publication (e.g. www.gvlines.com). The prices of these books are commonly around €1000. Figure 45 shows two examples.

Figure 45. Baby trend book by Minicool (left), Kid's trends book by Nexus Design (right).

Some agencies present book options that can also be viewed digitally. In some cases, these companies develop smaller, specific reports with more affordable prices (Figure 46 and Figure 47).

Figure 46. Kid's trends digital version by Trend Bible

Figure 47. Springwise innovation snapshots.

Spielwarenmesse, the Nuremberg's toy fair, publishes a free booklet that is distributed during the days of the fair to all the professionals interested (Figure 48).

Figure 48. Trend Book 2014 Spielwarenmesse.

7.2.4 AIJU's protocol for trend research

AIJU follows the methodology of work presented in the previous section, with their own specifications.

Firstly, it is necessary to have a historical review, retrospective knowledge. AIJU have been working in the toy sector for more than 25 years. During this time, AIJU's experts have been carrying out both social and market research to obtain information about how the toy industry and consumer behaviour is evolving. AIJU has an important library with publications and catalogues from companies that go back more than 25 years. All these reference materials are easily available to the trend team throughout the analysis and study of current trends.

Concerning the multidisciplinary team, AIJU's child research department has a team of experts in design, engineering, sociology, marketing, child psychology, and education that work together in the trend working sessions and meetings.

The following information describes the main research methodologies AIJU uses to create their trend information (Figure 49).

Figure 49. AIJU's trend research protocol.

1. Collect information

- Secondary sources: news, magazines, books, catalogues, websites, social networks.
- Visits: fairs, distribution, cosmopolitan cities.
- Interviews with companies and professionals from different areas of expertise (marketing, sales, management, engineering, design, etc.) to gather information about the opportunities and challenges they experience in their daily work and in each field.

2. Analysis and definition of trends

When the information is collected there are a series of working sessions in which the team studies all the data. The meeting room fills with a multitude of Post-its, cards, photographs and other materials (Figure 50). Then, the team analyses the content, organising it by finding connections between the data. The information is divided into groups to start determining the first trend ideas. Afterwards, we work on the proposals to find even more information and corroborate the possible trends. When we are sure about the trends, and their international impact, we work on naming them by choosing a word or two that describes the main idea behind the trend.

Figure 50. AIJU's trend analysis, working sessions.

3. Spreading the information

AIJU always makes a great effort to provide the information on their trend's results to the industry, with the main objective of improving companies to change successfully, and appeal to consumers with products and services that respond to the latest social and market trends.

Figure 51. AIJU's trend presentation.

To this end, AIJU presents the information at several events, from conferences to fairs, such as the Business Forum Spielwarenmesse and at the Kind + Jugend (Figure 51). We write articles that are published in international magazines and blogs. We are a regular contributor to the Spielwarenmesse blog and online magazine.

AIJU also publishes its own reports and publications in both digital and printed versions, most of them available for free (Figure 52).

Figure 52. Sample of AIJU's trend publications.

4. Consultancy services

While AIJU's articles and publications inform the industry as a whole, so that all toy companies (producers and retailers), no matter their size and importance, can obtain relevant data to help their business grow. We also offer consultancy services to companies that request assistance in the application of trends related to their specific characteristics and needs.

7.3 LEADING-EDGE TECHNOLOGY

7.3.1 Introduction

Being aware of the latest innovations related to technology is a key to the success of most companies' long term. The development of new technologies influences the way businesses can compete in the constantly evolving market. From improving manufacturing processes to creating innovative products that improve and add value to the life to the consumers.

7.3.2 Who carries out research on leading-edge technologies

Patent and trademark offices have databases of new inventions patented that can be consulted for free. These organisations also prepare custom reports on request by a stipulated cost.

Agencies that depend on the administration: In Spain, Italy and Portugal COTEC Foundation for Innovation (<http://cotec.es/>) is a private non-profit organisation whose mission is to promote innovation as an engine of economic and social development. The foundation is supported by private companies and local and regional administrations. They periodically publish a report on the main technological developments.

Universities: There are important international universities that develop research related to the development of new technologies. For instance, the well-known MIT (Massachusetts Institute of Technology) has multiple labs such as the MIT Game Lab, focused on exploring the potential of play. Most of the projects from the Game Lab involve the use of new technologies and its applications in the game industry. Other examples are the prestigious MIT Media Lab, a multidisciplinary research lab working to invent the future in several fields.

Private consultancies: There are companies that focus on giving advice to all sorts of business in that need support in different areas related to the implementation of new technologies. For example, DXC Technologies (<http://www.dxc.technology/>) or ARUP (<http://www.arup.com>).

Blogs and specialised websites: There are several blogs and websites that present the latest innovations in technologies applied to products. Trendhunter (www.trendhunter.com) or Kidscreen (<http://kidscreen.com>) are some of the most popular sites.

Crowdsourcing platforms: Today, websites to get crowdfunded to start a project are full of innovative ideas that are usually supported by the latest technologies. These platforms can be a great source for the industry to find partners in order to develop the next generation of innovative toys based on these technologies. A couple of the most known and used crowdfunding websites are Kickstarter (www.kickstarter.com) and Indiegogo (www.indiegogo.com/).

7.3.3 Leading-edge technologies information methodologies

Both European and National technological platforms develop specific roadmaps, either on a specific sector or on a concrete technology. These roadmaps are elaborated from questionnaires that are sent to the companies belonging to these sectors and are carried out with the help of experts from both universities and research centres.

There are several European Technology Platforms (ETPs)³¹. For instance, EFRA (The European Factories of the Future Research Association). They create roadmaps to provide free information on the future of manufacturing³².

National platforms such as MATERPLAT, the Advanced Materials and Nanomaterials Spanish Technological Platform, also publishes free documentation. Their latest report is titled MATERPLAT 2020: Roadmap de Innovación Tecnológica³³.

7.3.4 AIJU's protocol for analysing available leading-edge technologies

AIJU collaborates with AIMPLAS (The plastic Technology Centre) in their research of leading-edge technologies. AIMPLAS has software called SOFTVT, which automates search and localisation of relevant information in different sources and databases. The software already features predefined identified sources, but we also provide those AIJU considers of interest to our sector. The search is based on keywords that are defined and updated periodically depending on the needs and trends in the different technological industries.

The results are filtered according to the interest and the number of information that have been located about the same subject in different sources. That is, if news is only found in one blog, it doesn't have the same credibility as news that is published in 3 or 4 different sources.

With this filtered data, AIJU prepares a digital magazine with the most relevant news (Figure 53). The magazine is published online on a monthly basis. It can be accessed through this link: <http://www.aiju.info/03/publico/vigilancia.asp>. A mail with a digital version is also sent monthly to all 450 of AIJU's associates.

³¹ http://ec.europa.eu/research/innovation-union/index_en.cfm?pg=etp#etps

³² Efra's latest created document can be downloaded at: <http://www.effra.eu/index.php/research-a-innovation-65/factories-of-the-future-2020>.

³³³³ MATERPLAT 2020: Roadmap de Innovación Tecnológica can be downloaded at: <http://www.tecnologiaeinnovacion.defensa.gob.es/es-es/Contenido/Paginas/detallereferencia.aspx?referencialID=23>.

Figure 53. AIJU's digital magazine about technological innovations.

8 FABLABS BEST PRACTICES

8.1 FABLAB DEFINITION

FabLab is an international concept that started at MIT. The term FabLab is an abbreviation from Fabrication Laboratory and it is defined as: a small-scale workshop offering (personal) digital fabrication.

A FabLab is generally equipped with an array of flexible computer-controlled tools that cover several different length scales and various materials, with the aim to make "almost anything"³⁴.

MIT defines a Fab lab as a global network of local labs, enabling invention by providing access to tools for digital fabrication, which provides educational, technical, financial, and logistical assistance beyond what is available within one lab. Designs and processes developed in fab labs can be protected and sold however an inventor chooses, but should remain available for individuals to use and learn from³⁵.

8.2 FABLAB AWARENESS

Nearly half of the companies that were interviewed personally for this project knew what a "Fablab" is. Fablab awareness is very variable depending on the region of Europe that is analysed. For example, France has a very developed network of FabLabs and the concept is spread over many categories of people. In Germany, there seem to be groups of people who concentrate around a common passion, but they do have some help from the municipality. In Romania, very few people understand the concept, mostly because it's something new.

8.3 FABLAB ADAPTATION

Once the concept had been explained, nearly all of them evaluated this concept positively. Even so, a major barrier was detected for toy companies. This was related to property rights. Most of them were not used to working with open property and they preferred to pay directly for the service provided by the ToyLab. The toy companies who agreed with sharing the property rights were those that were used to manufacturing for other brands (white-label products) or licensing products. In addition, this barrier decreased if the original idea of the toy came from the ToyLab and the company focused its activity on producing and delivering the products to the shops.

³⁴ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Fab_lab

³⁵ <http://fab.cba.mit.edu/about/charter/>

8.4 MOST FREQUENT TECHNOLOGIES OFFERED

The results of desk research were carried out in order to obtain information about the most frequent technologies offered by FabLabs (Table 9).

Table 9. List of technological machines founded in European FabLabs.

Technological machines presented in European FabLabs	
3D printing	Mould Casting
3D Scanning	Pottery Wheel
Acrylic Bending Machine	Precision milling
Circuit production	Sandblasting
CNC Milling	Sewing machine
Drone	Soldering Station
Furnace	Thermostatic Basin
Hot String	Transfer press
Infrared oven	Vacuum Forming
Knitting machine	Vinyl cutting
Laser cut	VR
Lathing	Welding Machine

Table 10 shows the 521 worldwide FabLabs that were analysed.

Table 10. Location of FabLabs analysed.

Country	No. of FabLabs
Italy	98
France	89
Germany	37
Russia	27
United Kingdom	23
Spain	23
Georgia	22
Netherlands	22
Belgium	16
China	16
Portugal	15
Switzerland	15
Japan	13
Egypt	9
Poland	8
Austria	7

Country	No. of FabLabs
Denmark	7
Iceland	6
United Arab Emirates	5
Philippines	5
Ecuador	5
Finland	4
Ireland	4
Norway	4
Israel	4
Ukraine	3
Greece	3
Indonesia	3
Kuwait	3
Luxembourg	2
Jordan	2
Singapore	2
Romania	1

Country	No. of FabLabs
Hungary	1
Bulgaria	1
Czech Republic	1
Montenegro	1
Croatia	1
Sweden	1
Afghanistan	1
Bangladesh	1
Bahrain	1
French Guiana	1

Country	No. of FabLabs
Hong Kong	1
Kazakhstan	1
Malaysia	1
Malta	1
Oman	1
Palestine	1
Thailand	1
El Salvador	1
TOTAL	521

Most of the FabLabs analysed had similar technologies and, therefore, can perform similar baseline activities. Based on 521 FabLabs analysed, it can be concluded that 3D printing, laser cutting, CNC milling and vinyl cutting, circuit production, precision milling and 3D scanning are the most common technologies offered by a Fablab (Figure 54).

Figure 54. Most technologies used by FabLabs.

Main technologies used by FabLabs

(n=521)

SOURCE: FABLAB LECCE, FABLAB ROMANIA AND AIJU 2017

PART C: TOYLAB REQUIREMENTS IDENTIFICATION

9 TOYLAB DEFINITION

9.1 TOYLAB INITIAL CONCEPT APPROACH

ToyLabs envisions introducing a new model that will innovate the value network of SMEs, towards the direction of changing their market positioning & prospects in the Toy Industry, overcoming obstacles like geographical barriers and fragmented markets.

In particular, a multi-stakeholder co-creation network will be created, supported via an open ICT platform, that will bring together a toy manufacturer with other key players of the toy industry value network – FabLabs, toy security experts, toy user experts, suppliers, clients, etc. – to collaborate closely for the provision of new toys that will be user-oriented and will respond to a clear market demand. This ICT platform should be managed by a ToyLab entity (Figure 55).

Figure 55. ToyLab initial concept approach.

9.2 GENERALISED REQUIREMENTS IDENTIFICATION

The definition of the ToyLabs concept should be linked to the needs, problems and manufacturing processes of European toy companies.

9.2.1 Problem identification

Table 11 shows the problems identified in toy sector and support opportunities to be offered by ToyLabs.

Table 11. Problem identification.

TOY PHASES	TOY ACTIVITIES	PROBLEM DETECTED	POSSIBLE TOYLAB SUPPORT
IMMERSION			
Strategy definition			
Empathise	<i>Market & design research</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activity not done professionally by a considerable number of companies. • Time and money constraints 	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Companies carried out research studies with incorrect users • Information generated by their experiences in the toy sector and by their daily work 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Selection of suitable sample from user’s database regarding project needs to give the opportunity to the companies to carry out their own feedback from users ○ Awareness of its importance
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Companies carried out research studies themselves, without having expertise in this activity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Basic training to companies on research methodologies and techniques ○ Elaboration of ad-hoc protocols ○ Awareness of its importance
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do not know where to find trend information (both market and social trends) • Do not know how to interpret market and social trends 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Basic training on how to be an amateur coolhunter ○ Workshop to apply trends in the toy company

TOY PHASES	TOY ACTIVITIES	PROBLEM DETECTED	POSSIBLE TOYLAB SUPPORT
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Companies need to improve how to interpret the information provided by experts in children’s behaviour 	
Define	<i>Briefing</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No concrete briefings 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Generation of a templates with specific requirements for this activity
	<i>Price strategy³⁶</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sometimes companies do not manage this task properly 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Development of price monitoring tools
	<i>Project development and management</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sometimes companies have problems organising the schedule (time constraints) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Creation of a specific program Help in the timing task when a new toy launch is programmed

CONCEPTUAL DESIGN			
	<i>Idea generation and concept definition</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Non-defined procedure established for this activity in a considerable number of companies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training to companies
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Companies do not know how to come up with new ideas Some ideas come from inventors out of the company 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promote toy design competitions (professionals and for students) Inventors database Database of experts in children Give insights to toy companies as a starting point to develop new concepts Manage workshops with company workers to generate desirable concepts

³⁶ Key aspect for the industry. This decision will affect the future competitors of the new idea and for this reason is very important to be right

TOY PHASES	TOY ACTIVITIES	PROBLEM DETECTED	POSSIBLE TOYLAB SUPPORT
	<i>Prototype development</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Economic and time constraints 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Offer a service to develop company prototypes
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Doll sculptors are old and there are no direct replacements for them 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Training toy companies in traditional sculpture ○ Training toy companies in 3D modelling ○ Offer a 3D modelling service
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Necessity of plush pattern design specialists 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Database of experts
	<i>Marketing and content development</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need for definitions of the expectations and limits of this activity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Training toy companies
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Marketing departments do not work with designers as much as they should 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Awareness of its importance
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Marketing departments are limited to sales functions and do not participate in user research (Immersion stage) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Training toy companies ○ Offer this service to the companies
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Companies look for experts such as educators or designers in specific activities (e.g., art and crafts experts, mathematics experts) to provide content. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Database of experts ○ Offer the service to develop content for the products that companies are developing

TOY PHASES	TOY ACTIVITIES	PROBLEM DETECTED	POSSIBLE TOYLAB SUPPORT
DETAILED DESIGN			
	<i>Product engineering</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sometimes the production department receives unfeasible designs. Designers need to increase their knowledge in technical and safety aspects • Designers do not have knowledge in developing design in 3D programs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Train designers in engineering requirements ○ Train designers in safety requirements ○ Train designers in 3D modelling programs ○ Offer the service to transform 2D designs into 3D ○ Offer the service to digitise traditionally modelled toys into 3D
	<i>Mould development</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Very expensive activity • Difficulty of finding local suppliers • Time constraints 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Create a database of certified suppliers ○ Promote the development of this industry in Europe

PRODUCTION			
Pre-production	<i>Supplier management</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficulty of finding suppliers with specialised knowledge of some components (e.g., dolls eyes, etc.) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Create a database of certified suppliers
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sometimes, suppliers do not meet toy standards 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Work with suppliers to meet toy standards
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fabrics: when companies ask for a fabric they have bought previously, they do not always find the same fabric 	

TOY PHASES	TOY ACTIVITIES	PROBLEM DETECTED	POSSIBLE TOYLAB SUPPORT
	<i>Raw materials and components buying</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficulty of finding suppliers with specialised knowledge of some components 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Create a database of certified suppliers
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sometimes, suppliers do not meet toy standards 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Work with suppliers to meet toy standards
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fabrics: when companies ask for a fabric they have bought previously, they do not always find the same fabric 	
	<i>Manufacture of pre-series Forecast³⁷</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sometimes companies do not manage this task properly 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Create software to improve the accuracy of this decision (data mining)
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • They cannot forecast the number of units to produce or sell for innovative products, because previous data does not exist 	
Production	<i>Manufacture of production</i>		
	<i>Assembly</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Very expensive stage because it is normally based on hand-made activities that are difficult to automate 	

-
- ³⁷ Very important decision. If the companies produce more units than the sales, the product remains in the store, and clients associate the product as a failure. On the other hand, if they are produced a lower number of units than those required by the toy shops, products are perceived as a missed opportunity to make more money and some final users could be dissatisfied.

TOY PHASES	TOY ACTIVITIES	PROBLEM DETECTED	POSSIBLE TOYLAB SUPPORT
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> It is hard to find people with toy assembly knowledge 	
	<i>Half-finishing manufacturing</i>		
	<i>Quality Control</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Difficulty of monitoring the quality of the units produced in an outsourced company in a short period 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide quality control service for the outsourced companies (specially for the one located in countries out of Europe)

DELIVER			
Storage	<i>Storage</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Limitation of the space, and deterioration due to heat or temperature 	
Distribution	<i>Transport and logistic (from manufacture stores to toy shops)</i>	The distribution of SME companies in local stores is threatened by the gradual reduction of the latter	
Sales	<i>Product placement</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The location of the toy in the shop has a direct impact on its sales. However, this activity is not monitored by a large number of companies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Possible service for the ToyLab Training companies
	<i>Advertising</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> If a new product is advertised on television, it has a higher possibility of being positively evaluated by clients Some companies express that a good advertisement can sell a not very good toy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Create a database of certified suppliers experts in children's advertising

TOY PHASES	TOY ACTIVITIES	PROBLEM DETECTED	POSSIBLE TOYLAB SUPPORT
	<i>Shop assistance</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Very different requirements for each toy shop 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Create a good practice guide for the communication between manufacturers and toy shops

EVALUATION			
Desirability (people)	User appeal and suitability ³⁸	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Some companies carry out this activity internally with a non-representative sample (age, gender, number, etc.) and inexperienced interviewers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Offer the service to carry out these studies ○ Training to companies ○ Awareness of its importance
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Economic and time constraints • Companies require rapid or instant feedback to resolve some problems • Difficulty of assisting a high number of users. It is a high-cost labour activity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Express services to carry out these activities
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Representation of the users valuations in social media of the total of the society 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Service of analysis of users' feedback in social media ○ Service of test with users

³⁸ This is a key aspect for toy companies

TOY PHASES	TOY ACTIVITIES	PROBLEM DETECTED	POSSIBLE TOYLAB SUPPORT
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The concepts are at a very initial stage and is very difficult to make a correct evaluation with the available information • The degree of development of some ideas varies greatly, making it difficult to compare between various alternatives, due to the absence of a common template 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Generation of a templates with specific requirements for this activity
Viability (financial)	Sales analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficulty of comparing with competitors' products. • The available data (NPD) is perceived as being expensive by some companies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Possible service for the ToyLab ○ Service of test with users
	Cost analysis ³⁹	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sometimes companies do not manage this task properly 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Consultancy service to differentiate between the key and unessential aspects of the product in order to reduce the cost of the product
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The degree of development of some ideas varies greatly, making it difficult to compare between various alternatives, due to the absence of a common template The concepts are at a very initial stage and is very difficult to make a correct evaluation with the available information 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Generation of a templates with specific requirements for this activity

³⁹ Key aspect for the product. Has a direct impact on the price of the product

TOY PHASES	TOY ACTIVITIES	PROBLEM DETECTED	POSSIBLE TOYLAB SUPPORT
Feasibility (technical)	Safety certification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Some imported products do not certify these products even safety certifications are an essential aspect for a toy. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Key service for a ToyLab
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> When companies consult the toy standards, they have problems understanding them 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide safety information in a way that can be easily understood by toy companies
<i>General</i>	<i>Internal presentation</i> ⁴⁰	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Companies need to transfer concepts, information generated, etc. in an attractive and effective way 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Definition of procedures, a generation of templates for this issue Training on how to communicate in an effective and visual way
	<i>External presentation - Presentation to clients</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Commercial departments do not have enough detailed information about the products they are selling 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Awareness of team building (design and marketing) importance Awareness of communication importance

⁴⁰ This is a key activity, it is the moment when a manager will decide whether to continue with the development of the products or not, and the effort made at this stage is not comparable with the effort made for its design. A very well designed product could be presented in an incorrect way.

9.2.2 Service identification

The definition of the ToyLabs concept should be linked to the needs, problems and manufacturing process of European toy companies. For this reason, stakeholders were asked in the electronic survey about problems, obstacles, etc. that their companies encounter when developing and manufacturing new products. Figure 56, Figure 57 and Figure 58 show in which activities toy companies need more support regarding each stage of the process.

The manufacturing activities in which toy companies need more support in the pre-production stage (Figure 56) are:

- User test,
- Prototype development,
- Product design,
- Idea generation and concept definition

Regarding the production stage (Figure 57), most support is needed in:

- Certification and laboratory,
- Raw material and components buying,
- Supplier management

Concerning the post-production stage (Figure 58), activities which need more support are:

- Advertisement,
- User feedback collection,
- Market evolution,
- Product placement

Figure 56. Support needed in pre-production activities.

Figure 57. Support needed in production activities.

Figure 58. Support needed in post-production activities.

Q. Based on the problems, obstacles, etc. you encounter when developing and manufacturing new products in your company. In which activities do you need more support?

9.2.3 Stakeholder identification

One important aspect that should be considered for the definition of a ToyLab are the stakeholders that will be potential users of the ICT platform and/ or services. Table 12 gives a description of the main profiles detected and their value proposition, as a first approach in the initial stage of the project.

Table 12. Stakeholder identification.

PROFILE	DESCRIPTION	VALUE PROPOSITION
Manufacturers	A person, group, or company that owns or runs a manufacturing plant. Companies that are responsible of the whole process of creation a new toy, from its ideation to delivering the toy to the shops	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Capacity to produce other people designs, concepts or ideas • Capacity negotiate spaces in the toy stores through their contacts
Inventors	People or companies which offers new toy ideas, concepts or designs usually to manufacturers or distributors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Capacity to create new toy ideas
Designers	People or companies which offers new toy ideas, concepts or designs usually to manufacturers or distributors. Additionally they can evolve other people concepts or ideas to designs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Capacity to create new toy ideas • Capacity to transform ideas to designs
Engineers	People or companies which offers to evolve conceptual designs to more detailed stage which all the information needed for its mass production	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Capacity to evolve conceptual designs to more detailed stage which all the information needed for its mass production
User experts	Companies or persons which are experts and have the necessary infrastructure to test concepts, designs, prototypes and final products with final users (parents and children usually). The main variables that they use to analyse are: Level of appealing, usability and trend analysis.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Degree of appealing • Degree of usability • Consultancy regarding trend analysis for the generation of new concepts or ideas
Marketers	People or companies who are experts in the promotion of toys. Their main activities are: advertising, social media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advertisement management (creation of

PROFILE	DESCRIPTION	VALUE PROPOSITION
	management, product placement, sales and contact with distributors	<p>TV adverts, catalogues, radio, etc.)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social Media management
Market and design researchers	People or companies who are experts in the detection on market and user needs. Their expertise is based on the transformation of these insights into new opportunities for the market	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Capacity to identify insights and market gaps • Capacity to transform insights into requirements and new opportunities
Safety experts	People or companies who are experts in analysing and applying all the safety standards which affects to the toy industry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Safety certification and consultancy of concepts, designs, prototypes and final products
Suppliers	Companies which provides the necessary material, components and/ or machinery required by the manufacturers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mass production • Mould creation • Components • Materials
Distributors	Companies which owns toy stores or specific spaces for selling toys	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deliver the toys to the final users
Lawyers	A person whose profession is to represent clients in a court of law or to advise or act for them in other legal matters.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide the legal framework to guarantee the correct collaboration of the companies in their sharing of the property rights
FabLabs	FabLab is an international concept that started at MIT. The term FabLab is an abbreviation from Fabrication Laboratory and it is defined as: a small-scale workshop offering (personal) digital fabrication.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short series and prototype manufacture

10 CONCLUSIONS AND FURTHER WORK

10.1 CONCLUSIONS

The definition of the ToyLabs concept should be linked to the needs, problems and manufacturing process of European toy companies. Based on the results of the electronic and personal interviews carried out for this project, it can be concluded that the support ToyLabs offers companies should not be limited to the production of the toy. ToyLabs should be extended to the process of creation of a new toy, from its ideation until its sale.

As has been mentioned during this report, the most important manufacturing processes for the companies were:

- Certification and laboratory
- Generation of new ideas and new concepts definitions and product design
- Supplier management (creation of a supplier/experts contact lists certified by the ToyLabs), raw materials and components buying
- Costs analysis and price strategy
- Quality control (especially when communicating with outsourced companies)
- Half-finishing manufacturing and assembly
- Sales analysis, market evolution, user feedback and user assistance
- Transport and logistics

In addition, areas where toy companies would most value the support of a toy lab are:

- User test, user feedback, market evolution and product placement
- Certification and laboratory
- Raw materials and components buying
- Prototype development
- Product design
- Idea generation and concept definition
- Advertising

Furthermore, as was mentioned in point five of this report (Part A conclusions), European toy companies are more focused on the conceptual design, detailed design production, and the delivery phases than on the production phase. For this reason, the services offered by the TOYLABS should consider this fact.

Also mentioned in this point was that one of the main barriers for innovation in the toy industry is the absence of historical data for this type of product, and that clients and those in charge of making forecasts normally base their decisions on this type of data. For this reason, a core activity for TOYLABS as a dynamising agent should be to provide companies with enough information and methodologies for the internal and external presentation of new innovative toys, which is a key aspect for the success of the product, trying to avoid the 'Valley of Death'.

10.2 FURTHER WORK

This deliverable constitutes qualitative exploratory research, with in-depth analysis of toy manufacturing processes and needs, to support the definition of a TOYLAB. Although it cannot be considered to be a representation of the entire European toy industry. For that reason, future projects or work could focus just on this activity and achieve a high number of company responses from different European countries.

11 ANNEX 1. ETHICAL VALUES

11.1 INFORMATION LETTER

11.1.1 Survey

Dear Sir or Madam,

My name is Pablo Busó and I work for AIJU, the Research Institute for Children's Products and Leisure, based in Spain and specialising in toys and children's products.

I am contacting you regarding a European Project called ToyLabs*. The first objective of this project is **to identify existing and emerging processes and techniques in toy manufacturing**.

This study will form the basis of the Toy Lab concept, which will be extremely useful for the industry, making it more competitive and distinctive.

For these reasons, **we kindly ask for your collaboration in an online survey to gather your views on your needs regarding the services that Toy Lab could provide you**. To answer this **15 minutes'** questionnaire, please click on the link below:

<http://213.4.36.171/html/view/online.php?pid=TOYLAB2ENG>

If you believe you are not the most suitable person in your company to answer this survey, please forward this email to him or her or send an email to pbuso@aiju.info with his or her contact details.

If possible, we would appreciate receiving your questionnaire **before 6th April**.

Thank you in advance for your valuable time.

Pablo Busó

* ToyLabs is a project funded by the European Commission (EC) named *"Enabling an Open Innovation Model for EU Toy Industry SMEs through Co-Creation with FabLabs, Safety Experts and Customer Communities"* and its main goal is to create a multi-stakeholder network and consequently a multi-sided platform where key players in the toy industry value network (i.e. toy manufacturers, FabLabs, certification experts, childhood professionals, end customers etc.) are brought together and collaborate closely in order to come up with new, innovative toys and games. The consortium is composed of NTUA, the National Technical University of Athens; SLG,

the Singularlogic Romania Computer Applications SRL; Start smart SRL and Sport design SRL FabLabs; V-CUBE™ Verdes Innovations S.A. and Industria Auxiliar Juema S.L toy manufacturers, and AIJU.

11.1.2 Personal interview

Dear Sir or Madam,

My name is Pablo Busó and I work for AIJU, the Technological Institute for Children's Products and Leisure, based in Spain and specialising in toys and children's products.

As we, at AIJU, acknowledge you as an established and widely recognised company/organisation of the toy industry, I am contacting you to ask for your valuable contribution regarding a current European Project called ToyLabs*. In the context of this project, deep understanding of the current situation in the toy industry is required as well as an extensive analysis of existing and emerging processes and techniques for collaboration, co-creation and eventually innovation in this industry.

Currently, a great deal of relevant data has been compiled thanks to the collaboration of European toy companies in an online survey.

Therefore, **we kindly ask for your participation in a personal interview** in which we aspire to communicate to you the ToyLabs approach, while also getting your valuable feedback and learning from your experience in toy manufacturing specifically concerning its needs, processes and technologies.

The personal interview will be conducted by AIJU remotely by teleconference and will last approximately **90 minutes**. It can be arranged any day convenient for you from **20th to 24th of March**. Please find attached the questions that will guide the personal interview.

For your participation or any further information about the project, please respond to the following email: pbuso@aiju.info.

Finally, you are more than welcome to forward this email or provide us with the contact data of any person that you feel might be appropriate and prompt to participate in this workshop.

Thank you in advance for your valuable time and we hope to hear from you soon.

Best regards,

Pablo Busó

*ToyLabs is a project funded by the European Commission (EC) under the name “ToyLabs - Enabling an Open Innovation Model for EU Toy Industry SMEs through Co-Creation with FabLabs, Safety Experts and Customer Communities” and its main goal is to create a multi-stakeholder network and consequently a multi-sided platform where key players in the toy industry value network (i.e. toy manufacturers, FabLabs, certification experts, childhood professionals, end customers etc.) are brought together and collaborate closely in order to come up with new, innovative toys and games.

11.2 CONSENT FORM

11.2.1 Survey

Thank you for agreeing to participate in this study, which is part of the ToyLabs project. We kindly request that you respond honestly to the following questions. You can omit any information or answers that you do not wish to disclose.

The purpose of this questionnaire is to gather information on the **processes and techniques applied in toy manufacturing** – not to evaluate you – so remember, there are no right or wrong answers, we simply want to learn from you. The results of the study will be processed anonymously.

Please verify that you understand that your participation is voluntary and that you agree to participate by providing your honest and constructive input:

<input type="checkbox"/>	Yes
<input type="checkbox"/>	No (<i>questionnaire ends*</i>)

If you have any questions regarding your participation in this project, please contact our technical expert, Pablo Busó, via e-mail pbuso@aiju.info or phone +34 963 391 376.

** We appreciate your response. If, however, you have any questions or doubts that could change your mind if addressed, you can contact AIJU's technical expert Pablo Busó via e-mail pbuso@aiju.info or phone +34 963 391 376.*

11.2.2 Personal interview

- Participation in this survey is completely voluntary and you can always withdraw from the interview at any time.
- All data collected will be treated anonymously through a system of codes.
- All information gathered will only be used within the ToyLabs project

Do you agree with the fact that you have been fully informed about the intentions and objectives of the ToyLabs project and understand that you are under no obligation to respond to this survey?

COMPANY SIGNATURE

TECHNICIAN SIGNATURE

12 ANNEX 2. QUESTIONNAIRE

Dear Contributor

Thank you for agreeing to participate in this study, which is part of the ToyLabs project. We kindly request that you respond honestly to the following questions. You can omit any information or answers that you do not wish to disclose.

The purpose of this questionnaire is to gather information on the processes and techniques applied in toy manufacturing – not to evaluate you – so remember, there are no right or wrong answers, we simply want to learn from you. The results of the study will be processed anonymously.

Please verify that you understand that your participation is voluntary and that you agree to participate by providing your honest and constructive input:

If you have any questions regarding your participation in this project, please contact our technical expert, Pablo Busó via e-mail pbuso@aiju.info or phone +34 96.339.13.76

1. Please confirm that you work in the toy sector

[P1_TRABA_SECT]

Yes, I work in or for the toy sector..... 1
No, I neither work in nor for the toy sector (questionnaire ends*) 2

Salto:

Si P1_TRABA_SECT=(3) ir a fin cuestionario

[P2_PERFIL]

Accounting and Finance..... 1
Administration..... 2
Buyers 3
Commercial / Sales 4
Design..... 5
Engineering/ technical office 6
Human Resources 7
IT 8
Logistics..... 9
Manager / Director 10
Marketing..... 11
Production / Operations 12
Quality control..... 13
R&D..... 14
Test laboratory..... 15
Other (please specify)..... 16

Filtros:

Si NO P2_PERFIL=(15) ir a la siguiente

[P2_1OTRO_PERFIL]

2. Please indicate your profile (multiple choice)

Click on the arrow at the bottom right of the screen to move on to the next question.

3.1 Please indicate the name of the organisation you work at

[P3_1NOMBRE_ORGANZ]

Click on the arrow at the bottom right of the screen to move on to the next question.

3.2 Please indicate the size of your company

[P3_2TAMANO_EMPRJ]

- Micro (less than €2 million turnover) 1
- Small (between €2 and €9.99 million turnover) 2
- Medium (between €10 and €49.99 million turnover) 3
- Large (€50 million or more turnover) 4

3.3 Select the country where you work (multiple choice)

[P3_3PAIS_TRABAJE]

- Austria 2
- Belgium 3
- Bulgaria 4
- Croatia 6
- Cyprus 5
- Czech Republic 26
- Denmark 7
- Estonia 11
- Finland 12
- France 13
- Germany 1
- Greece 14
- Hungary 15
- Ireland 16
- Italy 17
- Latvia 18
- Lithuania 19
- Luxembourg 20
- Malta 21
- Netherlands 22
- Poland 23
- Portugal 24
- Romania 27
- Slovakia 8
- Slovenia 9
- Spain 10
- Sweden 28
- United Kingdom 25
- Others 29

Filtros:

Si NO P3_3PAIS_TRABAJE=(29) ir a la siguiente

[P3_10TR_PAIS_TRABAJ]

Click on the arrow at the bottom right of the screen to move on to the next question.

4.1 Select the continent where your company carries out product design (multiple choice).

[P4_1PAIS_DISENO]

- America 1
- Africa 2
- Asia 3
- Europe 4
- Oceania 5

Click on the arrow at the bottom right of the screen to move on to the next question.

4.2. Select the continent where your company manufactures (multiple choice).

[P4_2PAIS_FABRICAC]

- America 1
- Africa 2
- Asia 3
- Europe 4
- Oceania 5

Click on the arrow at the bottom right of the screen to move on to the next question.

5. Please select the category of products manufactured by your company. If your company manufactures in more than one category, please select the one with the highest number of units produced.

[P5_CAT_JUGUET]

ACTIVITY TOYS (swings, slides, gym set, etc.)	7
AQUATIC TOYS (inflatable PVC toys, bathing toys, etc.).....	6
ARTS AND CRAFTS MATERIALS AND RELATED ARTICLES (crayons, chalks, pens, scissors, etc.)	19
AUDIO/VISUAL EQUIPMENT (music boxes, simple computers, CD players, etc.)	3
BOOKS WITH PLAY VALUE	18
CONSTRUCTION TOYS AND PUZZLES	17
COSTUMES, DISGUISES AND MASKS (intended to imitate)....	23
DOLLS AND SOFT-FILLED TOYS.....	20
EXPERIMENTAL SETS (electrical, photographic sets, etc.)....	1
FUNCTIONAL TOYS (toolboxes, microscopes, typewriters, etc.)	11
GAME SETS (picture dominoes, simple matching games, board games, bingo, etc.)	22
MECHANICAL AND/OR ELECTRICAL DRIVEN VEHICLES (not intended to bear the mass of a child: trains that make noise, pull-back vehicles, track racing sets, action figure vehicles, etc.)	24
PLAY SCENES AND CONSTRUCTED MODELS (farms, garages, dollhouses, detailed and realistic cars, puppet theatres, etc.).....	21
PROJECTILE TOYS WITH LAUNCHING DEVICE (toys that eject balls, bows and arrows, etc.)	8
PUSH-ALONG TOYS AND WALKING AIDS (animals on wheels, boats, cars, etc.)	15
ROLE-PLAYING TOYS (for imitation of adult activities)	16
SAND-WATER TOYS.....	12
SKILL DEVELOPMENT TOYS (stacking blocks, shape sorters, sewing kits, modelling sets, etc.)	14
TOY COSMETICS	2
TOY MUSICAL INSTRUMENTS.....	5
TOY SPORTS EQUIPMENT AND BALLS.....	4
TOYS FOR BABIES TO LOOK AT, GRASPING AND/OR SQUEEZING (activity centres, teething, cribs and play gyms, etc.).....	13
TOYS INTENDED TO BEAR THE MASS OF A CHILD (ride-ons, vehicles with/ without battery, etc.)	10
TOYS INTENDED TO BE ENTERED BY A CHILD (soft houses or tents, rigid playhouses, play tunnels, etc.)	9
OTHER (please specify).....	25

6. Please indicate which of the following activities are carried out and/or are outsourced by your company in the category selected (multiple choice).

PREPRODUCTION

[P6_PRE_PRODUC]

	INSIDE THE COMPANY	OUTSOURCED	NOT DONE	DO NOT KNOW/NO OPINION

Briefing – strategic definition, project generation	1	2	3	4
Idea generation and concept definition	1	2	3	4
Product design	1	2	3	4
Prototype development	1	2	3	4
Quality	1	2	3	4
User test	1	2	3	4
Marketing content development	1	2	3	4
Product engineering	1	2	3	4
Cost analysis	1	2	3	4
Price strategy	1	2	3	4
Product presentation – internal and external	1	2	3	4
Forecast – estimation of number of units to produce	1	2	3	4
Mould development	1	2	3	4
Other (please specify)	1	2	3	4

Click on the arrow at the bottom right of the screen to move on to the next question.

7. Please indicate the importance of the activities when developing new products in the category selected (multiple choice)

PREPRODUCTION

[P7_IMP_PRE_PROD]

	<i>Low importance</i>	<i>Medium importance</i>	<i>Very importance</i>	<i>Key aspect</i>
Briefing – strategic definition, project generation	1	2	3	4
Idea generation and concept definition	1	2	3	4
Product design	1	2	3	4
Prototype development	1	2	3	4
Quality	1	2	3	4
User test	1	2	3	4
Marketing content development	1	2	3	4
Product engineering	1	2	3	4
Cost analysis	1	2	3	4
Price strategy	1	2	3	4
Product presentation – internal and external	1	2	3	4
Forecast – estimation of number of units to produce	1	2	3	4
Mould development	1	2	3	4

Click on the arrow at the bottom right of the screen to move on to the next question.

6. Please indicate which of the following activities are carried out and/or are outsourced by your company in the category selected (multiple choice).

PRODUCTION

[P6_PRODUC]

	<i>INSIDE THE COMPANY</i>	<i>OUTSOURCED</i>	<i>NOT DONE</i>	<i>DO NOT KNOW/NO OPINION</i>
Supplier management	1	2	3	4
Raw materials and components buying	1	2	3	4
Half-finishing manufacturing	1	2	3	4
Assembly	1	2	3	4
Safety experts – certification and laboratory	1	2	3	4
Storage	1	2	3	4

Other (please specify)	1	2	3	4
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Click on the arrow at the bottom right of the screen to move on to the next question.

7. Please indicate the importance of the activities when developing new products in the category selected (multiple choice)

PRODUCTION

[P7_IMP_PRODUC]

	<i>Low importance</i>	<i>Medium importance</i>	<i>Very importance</i>	<i>Key aspect</i>
Supplier management	1	2	3	4
Raw materials and components buying	1	2	3	4
Half-finishing manufacturing	1	2	3	4
Assembly	1	2	3	4
Safety experts – certification and laboratory	1	2	3	4
Storage	1	2	3	4

Click on the arrow at the bottom right of the screen to move on to the next question.

6. Please indicate which of the following activities are carried out and/or are outsourced by your company in the category selected (multiple choice).

POST PRODUCTION

[P6_POST_PROD]

	<i>INSIDE THE COMPANY</i>	<i>OUTSOURCED</i>	<i>NOT DONE</i>	<i>DO NOT KNOW/NO OPINION</i>
Transport and logistic	1	2	3	4
Product placement – product placement in the store	1	2	3	4
Advertisement – publicity, media planner	1	2	3	4
Shop assistance	1	2	3	4
User assistance	1	2	3	4
Sales analysis – market evolution	1	2	3	4
User feedback	1	2	3	4
Other (please specify)	1	2	3	4

Click on the arrow at the bottom right of the screen to move on to the next question.

7. Please indicate the importance of the activities when developing new products in the category selected (multiple choice)

POST PRODUCTION

	<i>Low importance</i>	<i>Medium importance</i>	<i>Very importance</i>	<i>Key aspect</i>
Transport and logistic	1	2	3	4
Product placement – product placement in the store	1	2	3	4
Advertisement – publicity, media planner	1	2	3	4
Shop assistance	1	2	3	4
User assistance	1	2	3	4
Sales analysis – market evolution	1	2	3	4
User feedback	1	2	3	4

Click on the arrow at the bottom right of the screen to move on to the next question.

8. Please indicate the activity you perform in your company when producing the products in this category regarding the materials used (NOT INCLUDING PACKAGING) (multiple choice)

[P8_ACT_REALIZ]

	<i>My Co. does not use this material</i>	<i>My Co. produces the raw materials</i>	<i>My Co. transforms the raw materials to manufacture the product</i>	<i>My Co. defines the specifications and others transform the raw materials</i>	<i>My Co. assembles half-finished products</i>	<i>My Co. stocks and distributes the final product</i>	<i>Dk/Na</i>
Plastics, additives, resins	6	1	2	3	4	5	7
Wood and derivatives	6	1	2	3	4	5	7
Metal	6	1	2	3	4	5	7
Textile	6	1	2	3	4	5	7
Paper and cardboard	6	1	2	3	4	5	7
Electric and electronic components	6	1	2	3	4	5	7
Others (please specify)	6	1	2	3	4	5	7

Click on the arrow at the bottom right of the screen to move on to the next question.

9. Please indicate the manufacturing processes used in your company regarding

PLASTICS, ADDITIVES AND/OR RESINS

[P9_PL_FAB]

	<i>INSIDE THE COMPANY</i>	<i>OUTSOURCED</i>	<i>NOT DONE</i>	<i>DO NOT KNOW/NO OPINION</i>
Injection moulding	1	2	3	4
Extrusion	1	2	3	4
Blow moulding	1	2	3	4
Rotational moulding	1	2	3	4
Additive manufacturing / 3D printing	1	2	3	4
Thermoforming	1	2	3	4
Laminating	1	2	3	4
Machining	1	2	3	4
Calendering	1	2	3	4
Coextrusion	1	2	3	4
Casting	1	2	3	4
Compounding	1	2	3	4
Filament winding	1	2	3	4
Vulcanising	1	2	3	4
Pultrusion	1	2	3	4
Others (please specify)	1	2	3	4

Click on the arrow at the bottom right of the screen to move on to the next question.

10. Please indicate when was the last time you invested in the following manufacturing processes.

PLASTICS, ADDITIVES AND/OR RESINS

[P10_PL_INVFAB]

	<i>5 years ago until now</i>	<i>6-10 years ago</i>	<i>More than 10 years ago</i>	<i>Dk/Na</i>
Injection moulding	1	2	3	4
Extrusion	1	2	3	4
Blow moulding	1	2	3	4
Rotational moulding	1	2	3	4
Additive manufacturing / 3D printing	1	2	3	4

Thermoforming	1	2	3	4
Laminating	1	2	3	4
Machining	1	2	3	4
Calendering	1	2	3	4
Coextrusion	1	2	3	4
Casting	1	2	3	4
Compounding	1	2	3	4
Filament winding	1	2	3	4
Vulcanising	1	2	3	4
Pultrusion	1	2	3	4

Click on the arrow at the bottom right of the screen to move on to the next question.

11. Please indicate the finishing processes used in your company regarding

PLASTICS, ADDITIVES AND/OR RESINS

[P11_PL_ACABAD]

	<i>PERFORMED IN COMPANY</i>	<i>OUTSOURCED</i>	<i>NOT DONE</i>	<i>DO NOT KNOW/NO OPINION</i>
Deburring	1	2	3	4
Painting	1	2	3	4
Coating	1	2	3	4
Adhesion	1	2	3	4
Polishing	1	2	3	4
Machining / Milling	1	2	3	4
Cutting	1	2	3	4
Others (please specify)	1	2	3	4

Click on the arrow at the bottom right of the screen to move on to the next question.

12. Please indicate when was the last time you invested in the following finishing processes.

PLASTICS, ADDITIVES AND/OR RESINS

[P12_PL_INVACB]

	<i>5 years ago until now</i>	<i>6-10 years ago</i>	<i>More than 10 years ago</i>	<i>Dk/Na</i>
Deburring	1	2	3	4
Painting	1	2	3	4
Coating	1	2	3	4
Adhesion	1	2	3	4
Polishing	1	2	3	4
Machining / Milling	1	2	3	4
Cutting	1	2	3	4

Click on the arrow at the bottom right of the screen to move on to the next question.

9. Please indicate the manufacturing processes used in your company regarding

WOOD AND DERIVATIVES

[P9_MD_FAB]

	<i>INSIDE THE COMPANY</i>	<i>OUTSOURCED</i>	<i>NOT DONE</i>	<i>DO NOT KNOW/NO OPINION</i>
Sawing	1	2	3	4
Debarking	1	2	3	4
Drying in a chamber	1	2	3	4
Brushing	1	2	3	4
Chipping or similar	1	2	3	4
Sheet metal cutting	1	2	3	4
Sheet wood cutting	1	2	3	4
Pressing operations	1	2	3	4
Edge banding	1	2	3	4
Drilling	1	2	3	4
Milling	1	2	3	4
Turning	1	2	3	4
Others (please specify)	1	2	3	4

Click on the arrow at the bottom right of the screen to move on to the next question.

10. Please indicate when was the last time you invested in the following manufacturing processes.

WOOD AND DERIVATIVES

[P10_MD_INVFAB]

	<i>5 years ago until now</i>	<i>6-10 years ago</i>	<i>More than 10 years ago</i>	<i>Dk/Na</i>
Sawing	1	2	3	4
Debarking	1	2	3	4
Drying in a chamber	1	2	3	4
Brushing	1	2	3	4
Chipping or similar	1	2	3	4
Sheet metal cutting	1	2	3	4
Sheet wood cutting	1	2	3	4
Pressing operations	1	2	3	4
Edge banding	1	2	3	4
Drilling	1	2	3	4
Milling	1	2	3	4
Turning	1	2	3	4

Click on the arrow at the bottom right of the screen to move on to the next question.

11. Please indicate the finishing processes used in your company regarding

WOOD AND DERIVATIVES

[P11_MD_ACABD]

	<i>INSIDE THE COMPANY</i>	<i>OUTSOURCED</i>	<i>NOT DONE</i>	<i>DO NOT KNOW/NO OPINION</i>
Sanding	1	2	3	4
Cleaning operations	1	2	3	4
Varnishing	1	2	3	4
Milling	1	2	3	4
Others (please specify)	1	2	3	4

Click on the arrow at the bottom right of the screen to move on to the next question.

12. Please indicate when was the last time you invested in the following finishing processes

WOOD AND DERIVATIVES

[P12_MD_INVACAB]

	5 years ago until now	6-10 years ago	More than 10 years ago	Dk/Na
Sanding	1	2	3	4
Cleaning operations	1	2	3	4
Varnishing	1	2	3	4
Milling	1	2	3	4

Click on the arrow at the bottom right of the screen to move on to the next question.

9. Please indicate the manufacturing processes used in your company regarding

METAL

[P9_MT_FAB]

	INSIDE THE COMPANY	OUTSOURCED	NOT DONE	DO NOT KNOW/NO OPINION
Additive manufacturing	1	2	3	4
Melting	1	2	3	4
Welding and joining technologies	1	2	3	4
Powder metallurgy	1	2	3	4
Machining	1	2	3	4
Conformation (stamping, bending of the sheets)	1	2	3	4
Sheet metal cutting (laser, water jet cutter)	1	2	3	4
Punching	1	2	3	4
Injection	1	2	3	4
Soldering	1	2	3	4
Metal casting	1	2	3	4
Sand casting	1	2	3	4
Cold lamination	1	2	3	4
Cold extrusion	1	2	3	4
Drilling	1	2	3	4
Milling	1	2	3	4
Turning	1	2	3	4
Others (please specify)	1	2	3	4

Click on the arrow at the bottom right of the screen to move on to the next question.

10. Please indicate when was the last time you invested in the following manufacturing processes.

METAL

[P10_MT_INVFAB]

	5 years ago until now	6-10 years ago	More than 10 years ago	Dk/Na
Additive manufacturing	1	2	3	4
Melting	1	2	3	4
Welding and joining technologies	1	2	3	4
Powder metallurgy	1	2	3	4
Machining	1	2	3	4
Conformation (stamping, bending of the sheets)	1	2	3	4
Sheet metal cutting (laser, water jet cutter)	1	2	3	4
Punching	1	2	3	4
Injection	1	2	3	4
Soldering	1	2	3	4
Metal casting	1	2	3	4

Sand casting	1	2	3	4
Cold lamination	1	2	3	4
Cold extrusion	1	2	3	4
Drilling	1	2	3	4
Milling	1	2	3	4
Turning	1	2	3	4

Click on the arrow at the bottom right of the screen to move on to the next question.

11. Please indicate the finishing processes used in your company regarding

METAL

[P11_MT_ACABAD]

	INSIDE THE COMPANY	OUTSOURCED	NOT DONE	DO NOT KNOW/NO OPINION
Polishing	1	2	3	4
Chip finishing	1	2	3	4
Abrasive grinding	1	2	3	4
Grinding	1	2	3	4
Lapping	1	2	3	4
Knurling	1	2	3	4
Burnishing	1	2	3	4
Chemical and electrochemical processes	1	2	3	4
Sandblasting	1	2	3	4
Reaming	1	2	3	4
Electrolytic coatings	1	2	3	4
Annealing	1	2	3	4
Galvanising	1	2	3	4
Anodising	1	2	3	4
Chrome plating	1	2	3	4
Surface and thermal treatments	1	2	3	4
Others (please specify)	1	2	3	4

Click on the arrow at the bottom right of the screen to move on to the next question.

12. Please indicate when was the last time you invested in the following finishing processes.

METAL

[P12_MT_INVACBD]

	5 years ago until now	6-10 years ago	More than 10 years ago	Dk/Na
Polishing	1	2	3	4
Chip finishing	1	2	3	4
Abrasive grinding	1	2	3	4
Grinding	1	2	3	4
Lapping	1	2	3	4
Knurling	1	2	3	4
Burnishing	1	2	3	4
Chemical and electrochemical processes	1	2	3	4
Sandblasting	1	2	3	4
Reaming	1	2	3	4
Electrolytic coatings	1	2	3	4
Annealing	1	2	3	4
Galvanising	1	2	3	4
Anodising	1	2	3	4
Chrome plating	1	2	3	4
Surface and thermal treatments	1	2	3	4

Click on the arrow at the bottom right of the screen to move on to the next question.

9. Please indicate the manufacturing processes used in your company regarding

TEXTILES

[P9_TX_FAB]

	INSIDE THE COMPANY	OUTSOURCED	NOT DONE	DO NOT KNOW/NO OPINION
Die cutting	1	2	3	4
CNC cutting	1	2	3	4
Laser cutting	1	2	3	4
Sewing	1	2	3	4
Spinning	1	2	3	4
Weaving	1	2	3	4
Tailoring	1	2	3	4
High frequency soldering	1	2	3	4
Others (please specify)	1	2	3	4

Click on the arrow at the bottom right of the screen to move on to the next question.

10. Please indicate when was the last time you invested in the following manufacturing processes.

TEXTILES

[P10_TX_INVFAB]

	5 years ago until now	6-10 years ago	More than 10 years ago	Dk/Na
Die cutting	1	2	3	4
CNC cutting	1	2	3	4
Laser cutting	1	2	3	4
Sewing	1	2	3	4
Spinning	1	2	3	4
Weaving	1	2	3	4
Tailoring	1	2	3	4
High frequency soldering	1	2	3	4

Click on the arrow at the bottom right of the screen to move on to the next question.

11. Please indicate the finishing processes used in your company regarding

TEXTILES

[P11_TX_ACABA]

	INSIDE THE COMPANY	OUTSOURCED	NOT DONE	DO NOT KNOW/NO OPINION
Stamping	1	2	3	4
Dyeing	1	2	3	4
Stiffening	1	2	3	4
Bleaching	1	2	3	4
Calendering	1	2	3	4
Printing	1	2	3	4
Stuffing filling	1	2	3	4
Others (please specify)	1	2	3	4

Click on the arrow at the bottom right of the screen to move on to the next question.

12. Please indicate when was the last time you invested in the following finishing processes.

TEXTILES

[P12_TX_INVACABD]

	5 years ago until now	6-10 years ago	More than 10 years ago	Dk/Na
Stamping	1	2	3	4
Dyeing	1	2	3	4
Stiffening	1	2	3	4

Bleaching	1	2	3	4
Calendering	1	2	3	4
Printing	1	2	3	4
Stuffing filling	1	2	3	4

Click on the arrow at the bottom right of the screen to move on to the next question.

9. Please indicate the manufacturing processes used in your company regarding

PAPER AND CARDBOARD

[P9_PC_FAB]

	<i>INSIDE THE COMPANY</i>	<i>OUTSOURCED</i>	<i>NOT DONE</i>	<i>DO NOT KNOW/NO OPINION</i>
Pressing	1	2	3	4
Drying	1	2	3	4
Calendering	1	2	3	4
Cutting and winding	1	2	3	4
Others (please specify)	1	2	3	4

Click on the arrow at the bottom right of the screen to move on to the next question.

10. Please indicate when was the last time you invested in the following manufacturing processes.

PAPER AND CARDBOARD

[P10_PC_INVFAB]

	<i>5 years ago until now</i>	<i>6-10 years ago</i>	<i>More than 10 years ago</i>	<i>Dk/Na</i>
Pressing	1	2	3	4
Drying	1	2	3	4
Calendering	1	2	3	4
Cutting and winding	1	2	3	4

Click on the arrow at the bottom right of the screen to move on to the next question.

11. Please indicate the finishing processes used in your company regarding

PAPER AND CARDBOARD

[P11_PC_ACABD]

	<i>INSIDE THE COMPANY</i>	<i>OUTSOURCED</i>	<i>NOT DONE</i>	<i>DO NOT KNOW/NO OPINION</i>
Satin	1	2	3	4
Coated	1	2	3	4
Bound	1	2	3	4
Folded	1	2	3	4
Perforated	1	2	3	4
Varnished	1	2	3	4
Laminated	1	2	3	4
Others (please specify)	1	2	3	4

Click on the arrow at the bottom right of the screen to move on to the next question.

12. Please indicate when was the last time you invested in the following finishing processes.

PAPER AND CARDBOARD

[P12_PC_INVACAB]

	<i>5 years ago until now</i>	<i>6-10 years ago</i>	<i>More than 10 years ago</i>	<i>Dk/Na</i>
Satin	1	2	3	4
Coated	1	2	3	4
Bound	1	2	3	4
Folded	1	2	3	4
Perforated	1	2	3	4
Varnished	1	2	3	4
Laminated	1	2	3	4

Click on the arrow at the bottom right of the screen to move on to the next question.

13. Please indicate which activity your company carries out regarding ELECTRIC AND ELECTRONIC COMPONENTS (multiple choice)

Filtros:
 Si NO P8_ACT_REALIZ_6=(1;2;3;4;5) ir a [P14_ACT_APOY_PREPRD]
 [P13_COMP_ELECT]
 My company manufactures electric and electronic components 1
 My company buys electric and electronic components2
 My company does not include electric or electronic components 3
 Others (please specify).....4

Filtros:
 Si NO P13_COMP_ELECT=(4) ir a la siguiente
 [P13_10TR_COMP_ELECT]

Click on the arrow at the bottom right of the screen to move on to the next question.

14. Based on the problems, obstacles, etc. you encounter when developing and manufacturing new products in your company. In which activities do you need more support?

[P14_ACT_APOY_PREPRD]
 Briefing – strategic definition, project generation 1
 Idea generation and concept definition2
 Product design.....3
 Prototypes development.....4
 Quality.....5
 User test6
 Marketing content development.....7
 Product engineering8
 Cost analysis.....9
 Price strategy10
 Product presentation – internal and external11
 Forecast – estimation of number of units to produce.....12
 Mould development.....13
 Other (please specify).....14
 None..... 15

Filtros:
 Si NO P14_ACT_APOY_PREPRD=(14) ir a la siguiente
 [P14_10TR_ACT_PREPR]

TOY COMPANY NEEDS

PREPRODUCTION

Click on the arrow at the bottom right of the screen to move on to the next question.

14.2 Based on the problems, obstacles, etc. you encounter when developing and manufacturing new products in your company. In which activities do you need more support?

PRODUCTION
 [P14_ACT_APOY_PROD]
 Supplier management..... 1
 Raw materials and components buying2
 Half-finishing manufacturing.....3
 Assembly.....4
 Certification and laboratory.....5
 Storage6
 Other (please specify).....7
 None.....8

Filtros:
 Si NO P14_ACT_APOY_PROD=(7) ir a la siguiente
 [P14_20TR_ACT_PROD]

Click on the arrow at the bottom right of the screen to move on to the next question.

14.3 Based on the problems, obstacles, etc. you encounter when developing and manufacturing new products in your company. In which activities do you need more support?

POST PRODUCTION

[P14_ACT_APOY_POSTPRO]

Transport and logistic.....	1
Product placement – product place in the store.....	2
Advertisement – publicity, media planner.....	3
Sales analysis.....	4
Shop assistance.....	5
User assistance.....	6
Market evolution.....	7
Other (please specify).....	8
None.....	9

Filtros:

Si NO P14_ACT_APOY_POSTPRO=(8) ir a la siguiente

[P14_10TR_ACT_POSTPR]

Click on the arrow at the bottom right of the screen to move on to the next question.

15. What other kind of support would be useful to your company?

[P15_OTRO_APOYO]

Click on the arrow at the bottom right of the screen to move on to the next question.

16. Is your company considering buying any of these technologies in the near future? (multiple choice)

[P16_TECN_ADQUIRIR]

3D printing.....	1
3D scanning.....	2
Acrylic bending machine.....	3
Circuit production.....	4
CNC milling.....	5
Drone.....	6
Furnace.....	7
Hot string.....	8
Knitting machine.....	9
Laser cutter.....	10
Lathing.....	11
Pottery wheel infrared oven.....	12
Precision milling.....	13
Sandblasting (cleaning, polishing).....	14
Sewing machine.....	15
Soldering station.....	16
Thermostatic basin.....	17
Transfer press.....	18
Vacuum forming.....	19
Vinyl cutting.....	20
Virtual reality.....	21
Welding machine.....	22
None.....	23
I do not know which technologies my company is using.....	24
I prefer not to share this information.....	25
Others (please specify).....	26

Filtros:

Si NO P16_TECN_ADQUIRIR=(26) ir a la siguiente

[P16_OTR_TECN]

Click on the arrow at the bottom right of the screen to move on to the next question.

17. What are, according to your experience, the manufacturing technology trends that will drive the toy industry in the next five years?

[P17_TENDENCIAS]

Click on the arrow at the bottom right of the screen to move on to the next question.

Before concluding the questionnaire, please indicate your email

Click on the arrow at the bottom right of the screen to move on to the next question.

[FIN]

Click here to end the questionnaire.....1

Thank you very much for participating in this questionnaire. Your input will greatly assist the success of the ToyLabs project and the improvement of the toy industry.

13 ANNEX 3. PERSONAL INTERVIEW GUIDELINE

/// COMPANY PROFILE ///

(To complete by the moderator)

Date _____ Company name _____

User name _____ Profile _____

Product category analysed _____

/// PRODUCTIVE PROCESS ///

Q1. Do you have a standard process for new product development? Please explain this process from the stage of ideation and conceptualisation of a new product up to its production (including concept definition, product design, safety assessment, prototyping etc.) *(Open question and the moderator arranges the answers in Sheet #1- top area)*

Q1a. Which are the particular activities that you carry out in each phase? *(Question to ask in case of respondent does not provide this kind of detailed information in Q1. It is an open question where the moderator arranges the answers in Sheet #1- "activities" area. (If needed, there are a list of activities in Sheet #2)*

(Open question and the moderator arranges the answers in sheet #1)

Q2. Do you collaborate with safety experts? 1. Yes _____ 2. No _____

If yes, at which steps of the production process? How do you exchange material?

Q3. Do you do your own prototyping? 1. Yes _____ 2. No _____

Q4. Do you have any external collaborators for prototyping?

1. Yes _____ 2. No _____

If yes (Q3 or Q4), how do you collaborate and exchange information/data?

Q5. Do you collect feedback from your consumers (end users)?

1. Yes _____ 2. No _____

Could you explain (in one-two sentences) how?

Q6. Do you use any technical platforms/IT systems today, related with production process? 1. Yes _____ 2. No _____

What do you do with these platforms/IT systems?

/// TOY COMPANIES NEEDS ///

Q7. Does your company have any problem carrying out the activities when developing new products? (Sheet #1)

(the moderator points out each stage and ask about problems. The moderator writes down the respondent answers in Sheet #1- "problems" area)

Q8. Which other kind of support would be most useful to your company? Please, think about everything involved, from the initial idea or briefing, to the product delivered to the consumer.

/// FABLAB ///

FabLab awareness

Q10. Do you know about FabLabs?

	Yes, I have hear about it and I know the aim of them
	Yes, I have hear about it but I do not know the aim of them
	No, I have not hear about them

FabLab explanation (show sheet #3 to support definition)

A **FabLab** (fabrication laboratory) is a small-scale workshop offering – personalised– digital fabrication. It is equipped with machines and technologies that

cover several different length scales and various materials. They can be used in all phases of product development and, therefore, allow the client or user to perform as much of the product development as possible in the FabLab.

Q11. After the explanation, do you know understand FabLabs goals?

1. Yes ___ 2. No___

(to explain to the respondent)

Who owns fab lab inventions? Designs and processes developed in fab labs can be protected and sold however an inventor chooses, but should remain available for individuals to use and learn from. FabLabs has some open source designs that can be used, but not commercialised.

Q12. Do you agree with this? How would you like to proceed?

--

/// TOYLAB ///

ToyLab explanation (show sheet #4 to support definition)

The idea of a **ToyLab** is focused on creating a Fab Lab specialised in the toy industry, offering expert services centred on toys and childhood, in order to come up with new, innovative toys and games.

ToyLab services

Q13. Which of the next services should have a ToyLab?

	Studies with users and knowledge about the target of the product
	Trend and social analysis
	Rent of manufacturing machines
	Consultancy regarding technology application
	Consultancy regarding grants
	Consultancy regarding manufacturing processes
	Consultancy regarding materials
	Certification

Q14. Is any kind of service that a Fab Lab could offer to your company not on the list? If so, please state what it is, indicate its positive and negatives aspects, and explain them. ToyLab ideal.

ToyLabs customer journey

Q15. Imagine a day when your company needs help at some stage of the design and/or manufacturing process. Please, describe how you would approach and communicate with the ToyLab.

Toy Labs appealing

Q16. What do you think about ToyLab concept?

/// SHEET #1: DESIGN AND MANUFACTURING PROCESS ///

Activities			
Problems			

/// SHEET #2: POSSIBLE ACTIVITIES CARRIED OUT IN A COMPANY ///

ACTIVITIES	PROBLEMS TO SOLVE
PREPRODUCTION	
Briefing -strategic definition, project generation-	
Idea generation and concept definition	
Product design	
Prototypes development	
Quality	
User test	
Marketing content development	
Product engineering	
Cost analysis	
Price strategy	
Product presentation -internal and external-	
Forecast -estimation of number of units to produce-	
Moulds development	
PRODUCTION	
Supplier management	
Raw materials and components buying	
Half-finishing manufacturing	
Assembly	
Certification and laboratory	
Storage	
POST PRODUCTION	
Transport and logistic	
Product placement -product place in the store-	
Advertisement -publicity, media planner-	
Sales analysis	
Shop assistance	
User assistance	
Market evolution	

/// SHEET #3: FABLABS ///

/// SHEET #4: TOYLABS ///

14 ANNEX 4. GLOSSARY OF TERMS AND DEFINITIONS

CHILD: Person age under fourteen years (ISO/IEC GUIDE 50:2014 (E)).

FABLAB: FabLab is an international concept that started at MIT. The term FabLab is an abbreviation from Fabrication Laboratory and it is defined as: a small-scale workshop offering (personal) digital fabrication.

ONLINE SURVEY: Is a questionnaire consisting of a series of questions and other prompts for the purpose of gathering information from respondents over the Internet. It is usually created as Web forms with a database to store the answers and statistical software to provide analytics (AIJU, 2017).

PILOT TEST: Also called pilot study or pilot experiment, is a small-scale preliminary study conducted in order to evaluate feasibility, time, cost and possible adverse events in an attempt to predict some problems and improve upon the design of the study prior to performing a full-scale research project. (AIJU, 2013).

PERSONAL INTERVIEW: Is a one-to-one conversation in which questions are asked to get specific answers. This allows to get information about people who are geographically far away from the interviewer. Interviews are usually face-to-face but new technologies are broadening the possibilities and they can be done with videoconferencing. The cost of the webcam-based interviews compared to having to travel where customers are, is helping this way of interviewing to become more common (AIJU, 2017).

TOY: Products designed or intended, whether or not exclusively, for use in play by children under 14 years of age (hereinafter referred to as toys). Directive 2009/48/EC of The European Parliament and of The Council shall not apply to the following toys: (a) playground equipment intended for public use; (b) automatic playing machines, whether coin operated or not, intended for public use; (c) toy vehicles equipped with combustion engines; (d) toy steam engines; and (e) slings and catapults.

TOY CATEGORY: A particular group of related products (CAMBRIDGE DICTIONARY)

TOYLAB: ToyLabs envisions introducing a new model that will innovate the value network of SMEs, towards the direction of changing their market positioning & prospects in the Toy Industry, overcoming obstacles like geographical barriers and fragmented markets (TOYLABS, 2017)

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15.1 DESIGN AND MANUFACTURING PROCESSES IN THE TOY SECTOR

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